

DIVINFOOD

Co-constructing interactive short and mid-tier food chains to value agrobiodiversity in healthy plant-based food

Deliverable D4.3

SMART indexes of agrobiodiversity use in breeding, and empirical data

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Executive summary

Deliverable 4.3 - "*SMART indexes of agrobiodiversity use in breeding, and empirical data*" presents indicators related to the benefits of investing in breeding of Neglected and Underutilised Crops (NUCs) through (i) genetic resources characterisation, maintenance and cultivation, (2) selection and adaptation *in situ* from available materials (i.e. dynamic management of genetic resources) and (3) multi-actor breeding programmes.

The key benefits are introduced and then summarised in eight SMART indicators based on the principles and activities of the DIVINFOOD Living Labs (LLs) in the task "Novel approaches for multi-actor breeding for local adaptation and product quality" (T4.2).

Each indicator is presented based on an "Indicator card" that includes background information, relevant references and how to measure it at breeding initiative level (STEP 1) and regional level (STEP 2). The general presentation of each indicator is followed by empirical data from the DIVINFOOD Living Labs. The document is complemented with empirical data from the self-evaluation of DIVINFOOD LLs for the STEP1 of all presented indicators.

Authors: The core text was prepared by Mariateresa Lazzaro (FiBL) based on the T4.2 DIVINFOOD project activities. Laurane Desoutter and Yuna Chiffolleau prepared the general introduction to SMART indexes in DIVINFOOD. The examples to present the indicators in the LLs context were developed by the respective involved partners: Axel Wurtz, Martin Krier, (4.2.2, 4.7.1), Dominique Desclaux (4.4.2, 4.5.1, 4.6.2), Marie-Helene Robin (4.2.2), Paolo Annicchiarico (4.2.1), Mariateresa Lazzaro and Christine Arncken (4.1.1), Carlotta Vaz Patto (4.3.1), Dylan Wallman (4.5.2, 4.5.3), Szilvia Bencze and Fruzsina (4.1.2), Domitille Makankubana and Jean-François Tedesco (4.4.1)

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1. General Introduction on SMART indexes in DIVINFOOD

The use of genotypes (G) in food value chains is typically evaluated at the level of the agricultural plot, in relation to the biophysical environment and the agricultural practices implemented. DIVINFOOD extends the analysis of the benefits of using genotypes to the level of the food value chain and the Living Lab region.

Furthermore, the use of genotypes in food value chains is typically assessed through agronomic and technological criteria, so that the benefits of using genotypes are essentially measured through indicators related to productivity (e.g., yield) and technological quality (e.g., protein rate). The DIVINFOOD project assumes that using genotypes generates a larger range of benefits, not reduced to the criteria and indicators which are promoted in the agro-industrial system.

The DIVINFOOD approach thus broadens the analysis of genotype-environment interactions, both from the point of view of the environment considered and the results measured. The classic equation **GxE = yield and technological quality**, where G = genetically homogeneous cultivars, and E = biophysical environment and agricultural practices, is here extended to **GxE = ecosystem services + other benefits + costs**, where G = a diversity of genetic resources (pure lines, populations, landraces, etc.) and E = biophysical environment, agricultural practices, processing techniques, marketing channels, social organisations and regulations.

Finally, the impacts of genotype use are typically evaluated through indicators measured using tools available in the laboratory (e.g., NIRS method to assess grain quality) and in relation to the objectives promoted in the agro-industrial system (yield maximisation, technological parameters for industrial processing). DIVINFOOD seeks to evaluate these impacts through SMART indicators which can be measured, as far as possible, by easy-to-use methods. SMART indicators are specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound indicators that are used in monitoring and evaluation; they help to ensure that the indicators chosen are well-defined and can be effectively measured to track progress towards specific goals.

In the DIVINFOOD project, the specific goals are, on one hand, to develop healthy plant-based foods and environmentally, economically and socially sustainable food systems. On the other hand, the goal is to support professionals, decision-makers and citizens in evaluating by themselves, as far as possible, the impacts of using genotypes (i.e. growing a certain type of cultivar, e.g. population vs pure line of a certain type of crop, e.g. rivet wheat instead of common wheat) in order to facilitate the collective management and monitoring of agrobiodiversity. The indicators and measurement methods must therefore be chosen in relation to these goals.

In the field of agrobiodiversity, DIVINFOOD targets genotypes related to neglected and underutilised crops (NUCs). NUCs are those to which little attention is paid or which are entirely ignored by agricultural researchers, plant breeders and policymakers (Padulosi et al., 2002¹). The neglect of NUCs is partly due to their low competitiveness compared with major crops, so that

¹ Padulosi, S., Hodgkin, T., Williams, J.T., Haq, N. 2002. Underutilized crops: trends, challenges and opportunities in the 21st Century. In: J.M.M. Engels, V.R. Rao, A.H.D. Brown, M.T. Jackson eds. Managing plant genetic diversity. Wallingford, UK: CABI Publishing; Rome: International Plant Genetic Resources Institute (IPGRI).

they have not attracted the interest of those involved in the agro-industrial system. In this sense, NUCs are giving rise to alternative environments to the agro-industrial environment for the use of genotypes. The DIVINFOOD project aims to highlight the benefits associated with interactions between NUC genotypes and these alternative environments, throughout the value chains considered in the LLs and at regional/country level. The objective is to propose SMART indicators to measure these benefits and to provide empirical data relating to these indicators.

A set of complementary deliverables presents the SMART indicators, and empirical data, related to the benefits resulting from the interactions between NUC genotypes and their environment of use in breeding (D4.3), cultivation (D3.5), food processing and eating (D2.3), and marketing (D1.4). All data are recorded in the database GxE developed in the WP5. Depending on the value chain stages, the proposed SMART indicators will not be fully measured in the time allotted to DIVINFOOD, but they are designed to be used by the actors involved in the field to evaluate and manage their activity around NUCs, and to compare the benefits gained from the use of these NUCs with those generated by major crops. This deliverable D4.3 is part of this set of deliverables and presents the SMART indicators and empirical data, related to the benefits, for the value chains considered in the LLs and for the regions/countries, of using NUC genotypes in plant breeding. For each SMART indicator, 2 steps of measurement will thus be proposed: STEP1, at the level of the value chains considered in the LLs, and STEP2 at the level of a region (which could be the LL region, the country, etc.). While the completion of the step 1 will provide empirical data to be used in the project, the formalisation of the step 2 will provide concrete support for stakeholders and policy-makers to assess the benefits of using agrobiodiversity at the level of a region (for instance, in relation with the agricultural/food policies which have been implemented at this level), and will be mobilised in WP5 of the project to formulate recommendations. This fine-tuning of the two measurement levels explains the one-month delay in the submission of the deliverable, but was very useful both in guiding the other deliverables dedicated to SMART indexes and in strengthening the link with WP5 and the database.

A final remark concerns the use of the term ‘indicator’, rather than the term ‘index’ mentioned in the DoA. The use of ‘index’ in the DoA was based on the idea that an index is intended to be easy to understand and useful for stakeholders (e.g. consumer price index). However, an index is also often understood as the synthesis of several indicators, which can ultimately limit its appropriation. We therefore finally opted for the term indicators, better understood by the living lab partners, even if some SMART indicators developed in the project are made up of several sub-indicators, and therefore can still be considered as indexes.

2. Background: relevance of genetic resources dynamic management and breeding programmes dedicated to NUCs

Some Neglected and under-utilised crops (NUCs), which have been historically overlooked by mainstream agriculture and research, including variety development, are now being recognized for their importance in food security, nutrition, and sustainable agriculture. These crops often

have unique nutritional profiles, adaptability to harsh environments and cultural significance for local communities, making them key players in efforts to diversify and increase the sustainability of agriculture and food systems.

The potential of (i) NUCs genetic resources maintenance, (ii) selection from available materials and (iii) new breeding programmes to support the promotion of cultivation and use of NUCs includes several aspects:

- *Diversification of Food Systems*

Just three major crops (maize, wheat, and rice) account for about 50% of the world's consumption of plant calories and protein, while 95% of global food needs are provided by only 30 plant species (FAO, 1999²). This narrow focus on a few crops has led to a loss of agricultural biodiversity and increased vulnerability to pests, diseases, and climate change.

Genetic resources use and breeding programmes for NUCs can help diversify our farming and food systems, making them more resilient and sustainable.

- *Climate Change Adaptation*

Many NUCs are well-adapted to marginal environments and can thrive under challenging conditions and can even be produced without the use of pesticides.

Selection and breeding programmes can further enhance these traits, developing varieties that are more resilient to climate change impacts such as drought, heat stress, and changing rainfall patterns, and better resist to pathogens and pests that are either newly emerging or already present, but becoming more virulent.

- *Nutritional Value*

NUCs often have superior nutritional profiles compared to major staple crops.

Breeding programmes can focus on enhancing these nutritional qualities, contributing to improved dietary diversity and health outcomes.

- *Preservation of Genetic Diversity*

NUCs play a crucial role in maintaining genetic diversity within agricultural systems. This diversity is essential for the long-term resilience of our food systems and provides a valuable resource for future crop improvement efforts.

Breeding can improve the productivity of NUCs or decrease their less advantageous characteristics, thus increasing their cultivation potential.

- *Cultural Significance*

Many NUCs have deep cultural roots and are integral to traditional farming systems and local cuisines. On the other hand, these crops are also very interesting as new crops in regions in which they were not traditionally cultivated (e.g. drought resistant species in regions that newly experience this problem because of climate change). In this context, NUCs cultivation and use can support cultural exchanges between traditional and new growing communities.

Breeding programmes can help preserve and improve these culturally important crops, supporting local food sovereignty and cultural heritage. At the same time breeding can help to introduce these crops in new environments.

- *Economic and governance diversification*

² Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. What is happening to agrobiodiversity? [In English]. [ONLINE] Available at: <http://www.fao.org/docrep/007/y5609e/y5609e02.htm#bm2> [Last accessed February 2025]

Just three agrochemical firms controlled more than half of the global proprietary seed market in 2011 (Howard, 2015³) and this trend is ongoing. At the same time, the focus of crop improvement is increasingly targeting only a few major cash-crops for which breeding investments can be refunded through royalties on the production and sale of seed (Messmer et al., 2015⁴).

Breeding programmes on NUCs are often of low interest for large firms and on the other side a very important focus for small and medium enterprises, including national breeding companies, and independent initiatives. The work on NUCs is essential for maintaining a diversity of players in the seed and breeding market and it supports job creation in Europe through small and medium companies.

Despite their potential, breeding programmes for NUCs face several **challenges**:

- *Limited Interest from Breeders and Funding Agencies*

Most breeders, even in the public sector, and funding agencies show little interest in NUCs. This lack of interest stems from limited market potential and consumer awareness. Many NUCs have niche markets or are primarily grown for subsistence, which can deter commercial breeding efforts. Breeding programmes for NUCs may not offer immediate economic returns, which can discourage investment from both public and private sectors focused on short-term gain. There is a lack of consumer awareness and consequent limited demand can make it difficult to justify public investment in NUCs breeding programmes.

- *Lack of Established Breeding tools*

Many NUCs lack the extensive research tools (e.g. high-quality genome sequence, molecular markers, phenotyping platform) available for major crops, making breeding efforts more challenging and time-consuming. Additionally, there is often a lack of basic agronomic and genetic information about NUCs, which can hinder the development of effective breeding strategies

- *Lack of knowledge of breeding need for organic and low-input agriculture*

Breeders working on NUCs for organic and low-input systems (particularly suited for NUCs cultivation) may require a different educational background that combines knowledge of organic agriculture principles with plant breeding techniques. Training and dedicated education programmes are needed to train a new generation of breeders who are competent in genetics and seed production but also aware of varietal needs and requirements for agro-ecological farming systems.

- *Limited Germplasm Availability*

The genetic resources for many NUCs are poorly represented and/or poorly characterised in the gene banks and research collections making it difficult for breeders to access diverse genetic material for improvement.

- *Basic Adaptation*

Many NUCs require basic adaptation work before more advanced breeding can begin, as they may not be fully domesticated. This initial phase of breeding can be time-consuming and resource-intensive.

- *Decoupling between increase in breeding research projects not reflected in seed production effort*

³ Howard, P. H. 2015. Intellectual property and consolidation in the seed industry. *Crop Science* 55 (6):2489–95. doi:10.2135/cropsci2014.09.0669

⁴ Messmer, M., K.-P. Wilbois, C. Baier, F. Schäfer, C. Arncken, D. Drexler, and I. Hildermann. 2015. Plant breeding techniques. An assessment for organic farming. FiBL, CH-Frick.

Very often, programmes on NUCs support research, selection and breeding but not the seed multiplication that actually makes the seed available to farmers who want to grow the crop. The lack of emphasis on seed multiplication creates a bottleneck that both prevents their larger use in farming and the practical application of scientific advances in NUCs.

- *Policy Focus on Major Crops & Regulatory Challenges*

Agricultural policies and funding often prioritize major crops, leaving limited resources for NUC research and development. This bias towards established crops creates a cycle where NUCs remain underfunded and understudied.

Many NUCs face regulatory hurdles in variety registration and seed production, and in the determination of the cultivation value and quality assessment as existing frameworks and examination standards are often designed for major crops.

Despite these challenges, developing adapted cultivars of NUCs is strategic to boost their cultivation and use. The goal is not to make them major crops but to establish a solid role in diversified crop rotations.

Beneficial strategies to support the cultivation and use of NUCs with breeding are:

- *Dynamic Management of Genetic Resources*

Breeding efforts should be coupled with initiatives to conserve and cultivate the genetic resources diversity, both in situ and ex situ.

- *Integration with Local Food Systems*

Breeding objectives should consider how NUCs can be integrated into existing and emerging local food systems, local value chains and culinary traditions, especially in areas of new introduction. Breeding programmes should emphasise the unique traits of NUCs, such as nutritional content, or specific flavor profiles, to differentiate them from major crops.

- *Participatory Plant Breeding*

Involving farmers and all actors of the value chain in the breeding process can help ensure that new varieties meet local needs and preferences, increasing the likelihood of usage. Participatory breeding allows to implement “custom breeding” that helps to move away from the general adaptation model to the local adaptation model. Specific and precise adjustment can be made to a given *terroir*, or even to a farm, taking into account the criteria desired by the farmers and citizens of the territory. This local expertise is a support adjusted to local public policies.

- *Link conservation of genetic resources and breeding of new cultivars with quality seed production*

Quality seed availability is necessary to bring emerging crops from “experimental” small-scale to “commercial” farm-scale cultivation. The conservation and breeding programmes should focus from the beginning on the seed production strategy. For NUCs it is often very difficult to find seed of recent varieties because the seed production is very limited. Genetic material development and test should go hand in hand with a seed production strategy.

In situ conservation and use, dynamic use of genetic resources and breeding programmes dedicated to neglected and under-utilised crops are increasingly relevant in addressing global challenges related to food security, nutrition, and climate change adaptation. By focusing on these

diverse and resilient crops, we can create more sustainable and resilient food systems while preserving agricultural biodiversity for future generations.

However, overcoming the challenges associated with NUC breeding requires concerted efforts from researchers, policymakers, and funding agencies to recognise and support the unique value these crops bring to global agriculture and food systems.

3. Why propose indicators in relation to NUC-breeding?

The proposal of indicators related to NUC breeding is useful insofar as it facilitates recognition of and promotion of the vital role these crops play in agricultural biodiversity, sustainability and food security. Primarily, these indicators serve to highlight the significant role that NUC-breeding plays in increasing cultivated diversity. This increased diversity can serve as a significant **incentive for reversing biodiversity loss in agricultural systems**. By expanding the genetic base of cultivated plants, NUC-breeding helps to preserve and utilise diverse plant genetic resources that might otherwise be lost, which is particularly important in the face of the genetic bottlenecks that have occurred in modern agriculture due to the overreliance on a limited number of high-yielding varieties. Furthermore, indicators related to NUC-breeding underscore its importance in **optimising the cultivation and use** of neglected and underutilised crops. Through targeted selection and/or breeding efforts, these crops can be adapted to specific local conditions, their yield and nutritional content can be improved, and their resistance to pests and diseases can be enhanced. The optimisations resulting from NUC-selection and breeding make NUCs more attractive to farmers and consumers alike, encouraging their wider adoption and contributing to both agricultural biodiversity and food security. Another critical aspect that these indicators can highlight is how cultivation, selection and breeding can increase the **delivery of ecosystem services**. For instance, breeding efforts can focus on developing varieties with enhanced pollinator attraction, which not only support bee populations but also improve overall ecosystem health. Similarly, breeding for enhanced root systems can improve soil structure and reduce erosion, while creating varieties with higher nitrogen fixation capabilities can reduce the need for synthetic fertilisers. The delivery of such ecosystem services is beneficial to the environment, and contributes to the development of farming systems that are more sustainable and resilient.

NUC-selection and breeding indicators also serve a function in the **market differentiation of breeding initiatives**, creating a favourable niche for small, independent efforts and breeding companies. In contradistinction to major crops, which are dominated by large corporations, NUCs offer opportunities for local adaptation, specialisation, and the development of unique, high-value products. This market differentiation can support the growth of diverse breeding programmes and contribute to a more decentralised and resilient seed system. The proposal of indicators related to NUC-breeding has also the potential to **inspire new farmers and networks to initiate independent conservation, selection and breeding initiatives**. By emphasising the potential of these underutilised resources, we can encourage a new generation of farmers, seed savers and breeders to explore innovative breeding techniques, preserve and enhance local crop varieties, develop community-based seed systems, and empower small-scale farmers and local communities. Furthermore, these indicators can assist in demonstrating to policymakers and

funding schemes the importance of focusing on NUC breeding in conjunction with major crops. NUCs can play a crucial role in diversifying food sources, improving nutrition security (especially in marginal areas), enhancing climate resilience, creating new market niches, and supporting local economies. By preserving agricultural biodiversity and associated traditional knowledge, NUC-breeding contributes to the broader goals of sustainable development and food security.

4. SMART Indicators related to Plant Breeding with empirical data from DIVINFOOD Living Labs

A list of eight indicators has been selected based on the experience and expertise of the DIVINFOOD Living Labs (LLs, see **Appendix 1 - Description of DIVINFOOD Living Labs**) and their work in T4.2 "Novel approaches for multi-actor breeding for local adaptation and product quality", without neglecting the interlinkages of the LLs activities across the project WPs, from consumption to cultivation to marketing and eating (**Table 1**).

For each indicator, the following sections describe:

- the background assumptions that guided the choice;
- what is assessed and valued by this indicator;
- how it is measured (STEP1 and STEP2);
- the most relevant references on the indicator topic;
- examples, including empirical data, of breeding initiatives that assess the target aspect from the DIVINFOOD Living Labs.

Table 1 List of proposed SMART indicators of agrobiodiversity use in breeding.

The fit of each indicator to the SMART framework is summarised by: ++ aspect fully covered; + aspect covered; - aspect not fully covered. This overview should ensure that indicators are well defined, practical and effective in measuring progress towards objectives.

	Indicators	Specific	Measurable	Achievable	Relevant	Time-bound
1	Agroecological breeding environments	++	++	+	++	+
2	Genetic diversity within cultivars	++	++	++	++	+
3	Added-value target traits	-	+	++	++	+
4	Multi-Actor involvement	+	+	++	++	+
5	Genetic resources mobilisation	-	+	++	+	+
6	Small and medium scale entrepreneurship in the breeding and seed sector and in rural areas	-	++	-	+	-
7	Farmer capacity building in breeding	+	++	++	++	-
8	Citizen awareness on agrobiodiversity benefits	-	-	-	++	-

4.1 Agroecological breeding environments

Indicator Card 1	Agroecological breeding environments
Background assumptions	
<p>The plant breeding environment is a combination of controlled and natural settings tailored to develop crop varieties that meet specific agricultural challenges. In particular, it refers to the specific conditions, practices, and goals under which plant breeding programs are conducted. It encompasses both natural and controlled factors that influence the development of new plant varieties.</p> <p>The environment directly affects the selection process by influencing the expression of traits. For example, stress conditions such as drought can highlight plants with superior tolerance, aiding in the selection of resilient varieties.</p> <p>NUCs are very often bred and selected in agroecological breeding environments, characterized by specific conditions and practices that align with sustainable and agroecological farming principles. Agroecological breeding focuses on developing varieties suited to specific environments, i.e. aims to enhance local adaptability.</p> <p>Breeding is conducted in environments with reduced dependence on off-farm inputs. This approach aims to develop varieties not only adapted to more sustainable agroecosystems but also that contributed to more sustainable agroecosystems. When focused on organic conditions, this breeding environment excludes synthetic pesticides, chemical fertilizers, and other synthetic inputs. This restriction pushes breeders to develop varieties with improved pest and disease resistance. The agroecological breeding environments encourage genetic diversity. This supports ecosystem health and enhances resilience to environmental stresses. In particular, organic breeding considers the entire agroecological system, focusing on interactions between microbes, plants, and soil. This perspective aims to create long-term resilience in food systems. In addition, organic breeding aims to support the organic farming objective of increasing crop rotation options and crop diversification, with a specific target for neglected and underutilised crops.</p> <p>Creating these specific breeding environment aims to develop varieties that are well-adapted to sustainable farming practices, resilient to environmental stresses, and capable of performing well with minimal external inputs.</p>	
What is valued	
<p>Development of agroecological breeding target environment that promotes the selection of resilient and robust varieties, such as in particular:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Variety testing in organic or low input systems of conventional breed varieties - Breeding in Low Input Conditions - Breeding for Organic Production - Organic Plant Breeding 	
How to measure	
<p>STEP 1 - breeding initiative level</p> <p>4-level scale from 1 neutral to 4 very positive⁵</p>	<p>STEP 2 – regional level</p>

⁵ Breeding in Organic or Low Input environment is valued as a benefit. Organic and Low Input breeding environments are particularly suited for NUCs variety development. Yet not having a specific focus on organic and low input has no negative connotation in itself. With this indicator we aim to show that while any NUCs breeding program is appreciated and supports the increase of cultivation of these crops, Organic and Low Input breeding present supplementary advantages that enhance their overall value.

<p>1. No focus on organic or low input breeding environment 2. Variety testing in organic or low input systems of conventional bred varieties 3. Medium degree of agroecological breeding environment integration (Breeding for Organic or Breeding for Low Input Conditions) 4. High degree of agroecological breeding environment integration (Organic Plant Breeding as of EU Organic regulation (2018/848) and IFOAM guidelines)</p>	<p><i>[Number of agroecological NUC breeding initiatives in the region^a]</i></p> <hr/> <p><i>[Total number of NUC breeding initiatives in the region]</i></p> <p>Which can be compared with</p> <p><i>[Number of agroecological breeding initiatives for the key major crop^b in the region]</i></p> <hr/> <p><i>[Total number of breeding initiatives for key major crop in the region]</i></p> <p>^a region definition: to be set to the most suitable scale for the evaluation purpose (e.g., Living Lab region, Country) – remark valid for all indicators</p> <p>^b major crop definition: wheat is suggested and, in case not suitable, other major crop relevant for the region of interest should be defined – remark valid for all indicators</p>
<p>References</p>	<p>Empirical data from DIVINFOOD Living Labs</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Position paper on Organic Plant Breeding (European Consortium for Organic Plant Breeding ECO-PB): link - IFOAM Position Paper : Compatibility of Breeding Techniques in Organic Systems : link - Definition of Breeding for Organic: link - Materials of the scientific events by the Eucarpia Section on Organic and Low Input Agriculture: link 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organic Lupin Breeding in Switzerland - Organic Emmer Breeding in Hungary

4.1.1 Organic Lupin Breeding in Switzerland

White lupin (*Lupinus albus* L.) yields protein rich grain of high nutritional quality. It provides valuable ecosystem services such as nitrogen fixation, deep rooting, active phosphorous mobilisation and pollinator attraction. Therefore, it is a particularly interesting crop for organic and agroecological farming systems. It is tolerant to frost in early development stages as well as to summer drought during maturation. Because of this, it is a good alternative to soybean in the temperate zones with cooler climate in spring.

Figure 1 View of DIVINFOOD project field day on 25-07-2023. Christine Arncken (FiBL) explains the most important lupin traits with the example of the commercial cultivars in the cultivar trial before the participatory evaluation of a set of FiBL breeding lines against commercial cultivars (Photo: Felipe Castelblanco).

The promotion of lupin cultivation in Switzerland is part of a strategic effort to increase domestic protein crop production, support sustainable farming practices and develop climate-resilient food systems. However, white lupin is currently underutilised due to major obstacles in crop production. The pathogen *Colletotrichum lupini*, agent of the lupin anthracnose disease, can cause severe yield reduction in regions with high disease pressure such as Switzerland. Additionally, the quinolizidine alkaloid content in the grain is often above the accepted threshold for direct human consumption (<200 mg/kg).

[FiBL plant breeding group](#) started its pre-breeding programme of white lupin in 2014. FiBL collaborates with gzkp (www.gzpk.ch), an organic, non-profit plant breeding organisation to jointly develop varieties for registration and release in Europe. The program is conducted in organic certified conditions.

Key Objectives of Swiss Organic Lupin Breeding are:

- *Anthracnose Resistance*: FiBL initiated the pre-breeding program for white lupin primarily aiming to develop anthracnose-resistant breeding material.
- *Low Alkaloid Content*: we are working to develop lines with stable low alkaloid content, which is crucial for direct use for food production without de-bittering step. The goal is to select sweet varieties with very low alkaloid levels (<200 mg/kg) while maintaining disease resistance.
- *Early Maturation*: Due to the integration of genetic material from Near Eastern and North African origins as resistance sources, early maturation is an important breeding goal to suit Swiss growing conditions.

Figure 2. View of FiBL's white lupin breeding nursery 2024. The breeding nursery is located on a certified organic farm, each year on a different field following the farm's crop rotation (photo: Mariateresa Lazzaro, FiBL).

The **benefits of conducting the white lupin breeding programme in organic conditions** include:

- ✓ Direct selection in the target environment (=organic conditions) allows to identify genotypes that are specifically adapted to the intended growing conditions. This approach maximizes the potential of fitting cultivars to the environment, rather than altering the environment to fit widely adapted cultivars.
- ✓ Breeding and selection is conducted under organic conditions to ensure that resulting varieties are well-adapted to organic farming practices.
- ✓ The genotypes are evaluated under conditions that closely resemble their intended use, leading to more reliable selection decisions.
- ✓ The impact of environmental factors (e.g. weed pressure, cycle of nutrient availability) specific to the organic growing conditions are accounted for during the selection.

Figure 3. Results of white lupin cultivar trial 2024, which included one breeding line and 9 commercial cultivars (Christine Arncken, FiBL).

For example, in the season 2024 with high anthracnose disease pressure and therefore low yield level overall (see horizontal bars with 2020-2024 averages against the 2024 only data in the barplot), the two varieties Frieda and Celina with increased resistance outperformed the older commercial cultivars that are susceptible, but (see violet box below bar-plot in **Figure 3**) the alkaloid content already in the seed source was far above the suggested threshold for direct use for human consumption. One of the FiBL’s breeding lines (Zuchtstamm 141, yellow label on the x-bar in **Figure 3**) performed similarly to Frieda for yield with the additional benefit of a much lower concentration of alkaloids in the grain, giving first preliminary results of the combined anthracnose and alkaloid selection in high-disease pressure environment. In 2025 more breeding lines will be available for uniformity and seed availability to be tested against the commercial cultivars at plot level.

4.1.2 Organic Emmer Breeding in Hungary

Emmer (*Triticum turgidum ssp. dicoccum*) is a hulled wheat, one of the first cereals to be domesticated in the Fertile Crescent, but it completely lost its importance with the appearance of naked wheat species (bread wheat and durum wheat). This was mainly due to some unfavourable characteristics. Emmer is a hulled wheat, it is tall and tends to lodge, and compared to modern wheat varieties it can only produce moderate yields. However, emmer possesses valuable traits of resistance to pests and diseases and tolerance to abiotic stresses and is increasingly used as a reservoir of useful genes in wheat breeding. It has excellent resistance characteristics to certain diseases, such as e.g. powdery mildew. It also has good *Fusarium* resistance, which makes its wholemeal applications especially safe. Cereal leaf beetle might cause severe damage in bread wheat and durum wheat under organic farming due to limited protection possibilities, but emmer was always avoided by this pest even under high pest pressure.

In some parts of the world, certain traditional foods prepared with *dicoccum* wheat are preferred due to their better taste, texture, and flavour. It is rich in bioactive compounds.

Figure 4. View of moderately lodged emmer field in organic farm at Hódmezővásárhely (2024). Emmer is gaining nowadays a growing interest as it is especially suitable for low-input farming conditions, therefore, it is a particularly interesting crop for organic and agroecological farming systems. (Photo: Fruzsina Szira)

In Hungary, the National List of Varieties includes emmer as optionally listed varieties and in 2023, only one emmer variety (Mv Hegyes, 2008) is registered in the plant variety database of the National Food Chain Safety Office. This limited number of available varieties has not only greatly hindered the spread of emmer, but also makes it difficult for farmers to choose emmer varieties that are well adapted to organic farming or have increased local adaptability. Expanding the range of varieties is therefore essential for low-input and organic farming.

In ÖMKi, participatory plant breeding approach for targeting farmers' needs and expanding the range of emmer varieties has started in 2020. ÖMKi has also collaborate with the Centre for Agricultural Research - Department of Cereal Breeding (Martonvásár) and National Food Chain Safety Office (national authority for variety registration). In 2024 ÖMKi has continued the breeding nursery programme based on the progeny of the selected breeding lines and Organic Heterogenous Materials (OHMs) of the EPO×DIC durum-emmer crosses (seven cross families, originated earlier with the aim of introducing advantageous quality and resistance traits to each species) on a field-scale test plot in Martonvásár. Further selections of the best materials were also carried out. Seeds of 17 hulled-grained emmer (PEPO×DIC) OHMs from the harvest of 2023 were further-sown in a small-plot (6 m²) trial in Szár for propagation. Selected number of materials (having enough seeds for a start) were offered to farmers interested in testing on their own fields in 2024 (**Figure 5**).

Figure 5. One-farm seed multiplication of the naked-grained emmer line, at Nagynyárád, Hungary 2024 (left). Kitchen scale pasta testing of the harvested yield (right) (Photo: Szilvia Bencze)

Organic Emmer breeding by ÖMKi in Hungary focuses thus primarily on:

- **creation of naked-grained emmer** OMHs and variety candidates – one of the major obstacles of the spread of emmer cultivation is that its grain is hulled so it needs a dehulling procession step. So, we initiated crosses in 2020 between EPO durum selected lines and emmer (*'dicoccum'*) landraces (EPO×DIC population) so that we got naked-grained emmer lines.
- **excellent disease resistance and weed-suppression ability** – emmer has above-average features on these traits but lacks rust resistance – under organic conditions as a selection environment we got lines with the best possible combination of resistance characteristics
- **high yield** – low-input conditions and extreme climatic events have a negative impact on yield, so we need to conduct breeding under conditions more realistic for organic production rather than focusing on maximizing yield potential as in the conventional approach.
- **high grain quality and better bread/pasta quality** – low-input environments require stable quality traits also in emmer, EPO×DIC population serves as a valuable gene-pool to this issue, too,
- **stem stability** – we counter select these unfavourable characters using the EPO×DIC population, while we also have shorter straw-types.

The benefits of conducting the emmer breeding programme under organic conditions include:

- we get adapted materials to low-input environments (which is typical to most Hungarian organic farms), this involves both adaptation capacity (resistance to climate extremes), better nutrient use efficiency and weed suppression ability when we breed *'in situ'*;
- small-scale producing farmers can also participate and can have access to the best performing OHM and organic variety candidates so they can find the most suitable cultivar, their competitiveness might be increased:
- this participatory manner also provides an opportunity for considering special needs of the farmers or the end-use-consumer's aspects. The farmers also maintain their material

- themselves dynamically, allowing both a natural adaptation process and the farmer-conducted selection process;
- promotion of seed sovereignty.

The complexity of plant breeding for low-input and organic farming conditions in particular requires value chain actors and stakeholders to interact and collaborate in order to address the specific needs of farmers or end-users. In addition to involving interested farmers by offering them breeding lines for on-farm seed multiplication (see also 4.5), ÖMKi regularly organises multi stakeholder meetings and field days open to all actors (see also 4.4), including farmers, processors, media people and representatives of national authorities, and participates in cereal festivals with tasting sessions to gather consumer feedback and ensure the involvement of a wide range of local actors. These activities also help to promote emmer in general.

4.2 Genetic diversity of cultivars

Indicator Card 2	Genetic diversity within cultivars
Background assumptions	
Higher genetic diversity between plants in the same cultivar allows to obtain several ecosystem services and some agronomic advantages. The genetic diversity within a cultivar contributes to improved resistance against diseases, pests, and environmental stresses, thereby providing more stable yields. Breeding programmes for NUCs often prioritize maintaining and enhancing agrobiodiversity, which also means giving priority to the use and selection of high genetic diversity cultivar such as: adapted landraces, open pollinated varieties, (evolutionary) populations, organic heterogeneous material (Info BOX 1) and organic varieties (Info BOX 1) . This aspect of NUCs breeding may conflict with traditional breeding approaches focused on uniformity (pure lines for the target crops in DIVINFOOD).	
What is valued	
Genetically heterogenous cultivars (adapted landraces, open pollinated varieties, populations, organic heterogeneous material and organic varieties)	
How to measure	
<p style="text-align: center;">STEP 1 - breeding initiative level</p> <p style="text-align: center;">4-level scale from 1 neutral to 4 very positive⁶</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No focus on genetically heterogenous cultivars 2. Development of cultivars with low level of genetic diversity (e.g. cultivar mixtures) 3. Development of cultivars with medium level of genetic diversity (e.g. selections within landraces, OP) 	<p style="text-align: center;">STEP 1 - regional level</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>[Number of NUC high genetic diversity cultivars released in the region in the last 5 years]</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;">Which can be compared with</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>[Total number of high genetic diversity cultivars released in the region in the last 5 years for the key major crop]</i></p>

⁶ Development and maintenance of genetically heterogenous cultivars is valued as a benefit, i.e. the benefit of increasing genetic diversity within a single field. No negative implication unless very high product homogeneity was required for market reasons. While any breeding programme focusing on NUCs is welcome, the ones who develop high genetic diversity cultivar have the additional benefit of including the key benefit of agrobiodiversity increase at field level.

<p>4. Development of cultivars with high of genetic diversity (e.g. Organic heterogeneous Material, Composite Cross Populations, Dynamic Populations)</p>	
<p>References</p>	<p>Empirical data from DIVINFOOD Living Labs</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Chable, V. et al. (2020). Embedding Cultivated Diversity in Society for Agro-Ecological Transition. Sustainability, 12(3), 784. https://doi.org/10.3390/su12030784 - Annicchiarico et al. (2023). Value of heterogeneous material and bulk breeding for inbred crops: a pea case study. Field Crops Research 293, 108831. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fcr.2023/108831 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A field-pea evolutionary population for Northern Italy to be registered as Organic Heterogeneous Material - Poulard wheat populations in France

Info BOX 1: Novel cultivar types defined in the EU Organic Regulation (2018/848)

Organic Heterogeneous Material (OHM) is a genetically and phenotypically highly diverse plant grouping within a single botanical taxon and produced in accordance with the EU Organic Regulation Art. 3 (18). It is therefore not considered a variety according to definition of Article 5(2) of Council Regulation (EC) No 2100/94 and also not a mixture of varieties. OHM can be generated by multiple crosses of diverse parental material (composite cross populations CCP) and/or on-farm management practices resulting in high genetic and phenotypic diversity. OHM is characterized by its dynamic nature to evolve and adapt to certain growing conditions and is intended to adapt to various biotic and abiotic stresses due to repeated natural and human selection and therefore is expected to change over time (EU 2021/1189). They can be commercialized without DUS and VCU testing after notification.

A list of notified OHMs is available on the GEVES (French official organisation for variety evaluation and seed testing) website <https://www.geves.fr/variety-seed-expertise/organic-agriculture/organic-heterogeneous-material/>

Organic Variety suitable for organic production (**OV**) means a variety which is characterized by a high level of genetic and some certain phenotypical diversity between individual reproductive units. For the production of organic varieties suitable for organic production, the organic breeding activities shall be conducted under organic conditions and shall focus on enhancement of genetic diversity, reliance on natural reproductive ability, as well as agronomic performance, disease resistance and adaptation to diverse local soil and climate conditions. All multiplication practices except meristem culture shall be carried out under certified organic management (Art. 3 (19), Annex II 1.8.4). Based on the implementing directives (EU 2022/1647 & 1648 there is a 7-year temporary derogations that allows easier registration of OV based on adjusted protocols for uniformity during the distinctiveness, uniformity, stability (DUS) test and ensures that the official multi-location trials to determine value for cultivation and use (VCU) are conducted under organic conditions.

More info on the GEVES website <https://www.geves.fr/organic-varieties-suitable-for-organic-production/>

4.2.1 A field-pea evolutionary population for Northern Italy to be registered as Organic Heterogeneous Material

Inbred crop varieties are typically inbred lines (i.e., genetically homogeneous material), mostly bred by single-seed descent. They may also be bred through bulk breeding, which involves the joint growth across various generations of segregating lines issued by a cross in environments close to the target environments. The segregating material is exposed to the effect of natural selection and possibly mass selection before being exploited as a source of inbred lines for evaluation and selection (**Figure 6**). Elite inbred lines may be grown in a mixture to produce a genetically heterogeneous variety type, which is mostly static, i.e., rebuilt every time from its component lines before cultivation (**Figure 6**). In addition, bulk breeding may also represent the first step in the development of evolutionary population (EPs), usually by pooling material from different crosses (**Figure 6**). As an alternative, EPs may be created by pooling segregating material from different crosses in the first place (as a composite cross population). In any case, the EPs undergo several generations of natural selection in environments closely matching the target environments (with possible additional mass selection by stakeholders), before being possibly proposed for cultivation as Organic Heterogeneous Material (the only marketing opportunity for heterogeneous cultivars so far in Europe). The EPs could be considered as a sort of modern landraces and, as such, may undergo further evolution for adaptation to the conditions of specific farms (**Figure 6**). Genetically heterogeneous cultivars (EPs and line mixtures) have mostly been studied in small-grain cereals, where they usually displayed higher yield stability than inbred line material along with somewhat lower mean yield compared with the top-yielding inbred line commercial or parent cultivar. A recent study on pea compared the variety types in **Figure 6** across diversified environments of Northern and Central Italy, highlighting the high agronomic value of heterogeneous material. The line mixture type maximized the yield reliability (as combination of mean yield and yield stability), but EP material performed well and was less expensive to breed. Selecting EPs may be convenient also for breeding programs oriented to inbred line selection, as they may represent a dynamic management of elite germplasm collections to be used strategically as a source of inbred lines.

Figure 6. Representation of some breeding schemes for inbred crops: single-seed descent-based selection of a pure line, bulk breeding-based selection of a pure line, mixture of pure lines, and selection of an evolutionary population (modified from Annicchiarico et al., 2023, Field Crops Res. 293, 108831).

Within DIVINFOOD, CREA is performing two research activities focusing on pea EPs for Northern Italy (**Figure 7**): (a) the experimental comparison in pure stand (PS) and in mixed stand (MS, i.e. intercropping) with cereals of two populations that evolved for several generations either in PS or in MS under CREA's on-station conditions in Lodi; (b) the further two-year evolution of the population that evolved in PS in a specific organic farm, to verify whether any yield improvement due to adaptation to the farm conditions could arise relative to the population that evolved under on-station condition.

The EPs, which, originated from crosses among six elite semi-dwarf, semi-leafless parent cultivars with high yielding ability and yield stability in previous studies, underwent several generations of natural selection (from pooled F₂ seed) in their target PS or MS conditions.

The first activity, which included in the comparison also the parent cultivars and inbred line material from the same genetic base selected for either cropping condition, has been completed after a two-year testing work encompassing one year of testing under conventional management and a second year in an organic farm. The evaluation also a farmers' acceptability assessment based on a 9-level visual score attributed by a group of organic farmers.

Pea in intercropping was at competitive disadvantage (with an average pea proportion of 24% on total crop grain yield). The EPs displayed definite specific adaptation to the condition of MS or PS under which they had evolved. The EP that evolved in MS showed grain yield and competitive ability in this condition that were higher than the average value of its parent cultivars and very similar to those of the best-performing parent cultivar. Likewise, the EP that evolved in PS showed grain yield in PS very similar to that of the top-yielding parent cultivar, along with top-ranking total biomass, and higher values of farmers' acceptability, resistance to *Ascochyta* blight and plant height than the mean of its parent cultivars. On average, the EPs were higher yielding in MS and as yielding in PS than the average of the inbred lines specifically-selected for these growing conditions, but the top-yielding inbred line out-yielded the relevant EP in the target growing condition.

The EP that evolved in PS is going to be registered as Organic Heterogeneous Material under the name of Ellen.

The second research activity is on-going, with a final testing experiment performed in the last project year.

Figure 7. Evolution of the two pea population in intercropping with cereals (left) or in pure stand (right) (Photo: Paolo Annicchiarico, CREA-ZA)

4.2.2 Poulard wheat populations in France

Poulard, or Rivet wheat, *Triticum turgidum subsp. turgidum*, is close to durum wheat. It was cultivated in the 20th century in France for pasta production, but has been abandoned because its morphology was unsuitable for industrial agriculture (low yield, high size, lodging in rich soils). Poulard wheat has been tested on the Purpan experimental farm (Lamothe) for about 10 years in order to characterize different qualities such as sanitary quality (presence of diseases as *Fusarium sp.* and mycotoxins), agronomic quality (tolerance to pests as weeds, to lodging, precocity), organoleptic quality and technological quality for processing. All these years of experimentation have enabled us to differentiate the most promising cultivars in order to be able to offer these selected populations to farmers in pure or mixed form.

In DIVINFOOD, 11 rivet wheat populations provided by farmers and associations who have preserved them and made them evolve, were tested in 2022 and 2023 in 2 research stations in the LL region. Varieties have been evaluated by farmers, small-scale processors, technicians, citizens, researchers and students).

The selection program has been conducted to contribute to the local food system. It involved many stakeholders (e.g. researchers, farmers, processors, students) including consumers (with tastings for example), who participated during the field days organised to visit the experimental fields (June 2022, June 2023 and 2024, 50 participants each).

The major objective of the breeding program is to combine consumer acceptance, nutritional interests, agronomical data, and processing qualities (technological, and chemical).

For the farmers growing cereals for the small scale pasta processor, growing rivet wheat population have many benefits: they can collectively select (mass selection) a bouquet of the better mix. The project ensures that the individual cultivars are still multiplied separately since there is sometimes the need of single lines inputs in the population for the processing needs (e.g. need of a bit of durum wheat, that tends to disappear in the population, for its technological characteristics).

One of the main difficulty with the direct use of the mixed population is to give feedback in a very short period of time, in order to adapt populations for the next years. In fact, after harvesting in June and July, processing trials (milling, pasta processing) are done from September to adapt the population for sowing period (from mid-October).

Figure 8. View of DIVINFOOD Poulard wheat population trial at the Lamothe Campus in 2024 (Photo: Daphné BLONDEL)

From 2024, participatory selection days have also been held in the fields, at the producers' farms. The aims of these days are:

- Selection of heads for the collection of cereals to be planted next year,
- Development of wheat mixtures.

These selection days are based on the creation of wheat bundles in which only individuals that meet the selection criteria defined by the farmers are collected. At present, the main criteria are diversity, height and stem thickness to limit lodging, and productivity by selecting the largest ears.

4.3 Added-value target traits

Indicator Card 3	Added-value target traits
Background assumptions	
<p>In order to maximize the advantages of agrobiodiversity, NUCs breeding programs should shift their focus beyond mere productivity to encompass a wider range of traits that enhance both the functionality and quality of crops. This holistic approach involves prioritizing functional traits such as the ones that optimize intercropping systems, improve crop rotation compatibility, and bolster resistance to pests and diseases.</p> <p>Simultaneously, breeders should pay increased attention to food quality and taste characteristics, as well as traits that facilitate more efficient food processing. By concentrating on this plurality of "added-value" traits, breeding efforts can create NUCs cultivars that not only yield well but also offer superior nutritional content, better flavor profiles, and improved adaptability to diverse agricultural systems. This multifaceted breeding strategy has the potential to produce varieties that are more resilient, sustainable, and aligned with consumer preferences.</p>	
What is valued	
Focusing on a plurality of traits & Focusing on "added-value" traits beside productivity: Food Quality and taste traits Food processing related traits	
How to measure	
<p style="text-align: center;">STEP 1 - breeding initiative level</p> <p style="text-align: center;">4-level scale from 1 neutral to 4 very positive⁷</p> <p>1. No focus on added value traits (i. e. focus only on agronomic traits)</p> <p>2. Low level of integration of added value traits in the breeding programme (i.e. test for protein, antinutritional compounds)</p> <p>3. Moderate level of integration of added value traits in the breeding program (Full nutritional testing and sensorics testing on seeds or integration of focus on multiple stresses or particular cropping systems as intercropping)</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">STEP 2 – regional level</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>[Number of NUC breeding initiatives focusing on added-value traits in the region]</i></p> <hr style="width: 20%; margin: auto;"/> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>[Total number of NUC breeding initiatives in the region]</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;">Which can be compared with</p>

⁷ Developing resilient cultivars with high added-value (for biodiversity and/or for nutrition and/or value chain) is valued as a benefit. While any breeding programme focusing on NUCs is welcome, the ones who focus on traits beyond productivity (which is anyway important) have the additional benefit of delivering cultivars with added-value traits. In general, a positive effect of breeding can be expected in including the NUC in the value chain from cultivation to use.

<p>4. High level of integration of added value traits in the breeding programme (sensorics testing on the end product, test on texture and functionality of the varieties, food with new varieties of the NUC available on the market, focus on several agroecological traits)</p>	<p>[Number of major crop breeding initiatives focusing on added-value traits in the region]</p> <hr/> <p>[Total number of major crop breeding initiatives in the region]</p>
<p>References</p>	<p>Empirical data from DIVINFOOD Living Labs</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Edith T. Lammerts van Bueren, James R. Myers (Editors), Organic Crop Breeding. First published:16 December 2011, DOI:10.1002/9781119945932 - Gonçalves et al., 2022. Exploring grass pea (<i>Lathyrus sativus</i> L.) genetic diversity in Mediterranean changing climate conditions. European Journal of Agronomy 156: 127142. DOI:10.1016/j.eja.2024.127142 - Sanches et al., 2024. Grass pea (<i>Lathyrus sativus</i>) interesting panoply of mechanisms to cope with contrasting water stress conditions – a controlled study of sub populational differences in a worldwide collection of accessions. Agricultural Water Management 292: 108664. DOI:10.1016/j.agwat.2023.108664 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increasing nutritional value and climate resilience of Grass pea in Portugal

4.3.1 Increasing nutritional value and climate resilience of Grass pea in Portugal

In the year 2014, and after a few isolated research initiatives, a multidisciplinary team of Portuguese researchers concluded that grass pea (*Lathyrus sativus*) could respond to sustainability and health concerns not only of farmers but also of consumers and agro-industries in Portugal. However, in Portugal as in the rest of Europe, there was a reduced consumption of grain legumes (and grass pea was no exception), with its cultivation in constant decline. To reverse this situation, this group of researchers decided to bet on a greater alignment of plant breeding objectives and food innovation with the preferences not only of farmers, but also of processors and consumers through a more participatory research.

To do so, contacts were established with grass pea farmers and the local Municipality of the main national production region (Alvaiázere), and a participatory research project was initiated in 2015 as an attempt to adapt scientific innovation provided by plant breeders/geneticists, food chemists and microbiologists (from ITQB-UNL, iBET and CookLab) to the needs and criteria of farmers, and other stakeholders (with the support of Alvaiázere Municipality).

No registered grass pea variety exists in Portugal, so farmers cultivate traditional landraces selected over centuries of cultivation, but with reduced yields. During this project a wide collection of national and international grass pea accessions was gather and characterized at phenotypic and molecular level (**Figure 9**).

Figure 9. Participatory phenotyping characterization, at Alvaiázere, Portugal field trials, of the worldwide collection of 180 grass pea accessions that served as input to search for sources of interesting breeding traits (Photo: Carlota Vaz Patto).

The traits that were considered, **in addition to yield**, have been optimized throughout the years by a constant adjustment resultant from the researchers-farmers close interaction.

As an example, **resistance to root diseases like *Fusarium* wilt** or **to seed pests, like *Bruchus* weevils (Figure 10)** entered the trait list on request by farmers.

a.

b.

Figure 10. a) *Bruchus* weevils infestation frequency distribution from field trials at Alvaiázere, Portugal, in the worldwide collection of 180 grass pea accessions that served as input to search for sources of interesting breeding traits. b) Grass pea seeds damaged by *Bruchus* weevils. (Photo: Carlota Vaz Patto)

On the other hand, researchers have stressed the importance of **particular health beneficial compounds contents on seeds** (bioactive compounds such as the antioxidants phenolic compounds, **Figure 11**), not easy to score visually but with a potential impact on consumer choices (due to their effect on taste).

Figure 11. Seed Total Phenolic Content (in mg of gallic acid equivalents per g of seed flour in dry weight) frequency distribution from field trials at Alvaiázere, Portugal, in the worldwide collection of 180 grass pea accessions that served as input to search for sources of interesting breeding traits plus 15 Portuguese landraces.

Cost efficient selection tools (associated molecular markers and spectroscopic models) have been generated particularly for some of the most difficult to score traits, and interesting sources of the studied traits have been identified.

Ten years after, and within the DIVINFOOD project, we have extended this participatory network to more grass pea farmers and include also small processors (represented now both by ADECA association).

Due to a higher weather uncertainty in the Alvaiázere region in the last few years, that devastated local harvests, traits like **drought and flood tolerance** have also been evaluated on the original collection of grass pea accessions with double tolerant sources identified.

Presently, and due to an increase frequency of aphid infestations (may be related to increase average temperatures under field), farmers requested also to consider **aphid resistance** in the pre breeding screenings as a way to avoid any pesticide applications. On the other hand, small processors involved in the network, expressed their interest on the availability of **different seed sizes** varieties (**Figure 12**), to allow different processing objectives (flour vs. whole seed uses).

a.

b.

Figure 12. a) 100-seed weight frequency distribution from field trials at Alvaiázere, Portugal, in a worldwide collection of 180 grass pea accessions, that served as input to search for sources of interesting breeding traits. b) Small and large seed grass pea varieties. (Photo: Carlota Vaz Patto)

The developed selection tools and the identified sources of tolerance or resistance are redirecting in a collaborative effort the grass pea improvement so that these characteristics appear combined in new varieties.

Pre-breeding plant materials, which include a combination of desirable characteristics of quality, resistance and productivity, are currently being developed through controlled crossing among interesting sources and local landraces, and advanced materials will be selected in collaboration with farmers and small processors.

4.4 Multi-actor involvement

Indicator Card 4		Multi-actor involvement
Background assumptions		
<p>Participatory plant breeding (PPB) offers numerous advantages by actively involving farmers and other stakeholders across the value chain in the crop improvement process. This collaborative approach ensures that new varieties are tailored to meet the specific needs and preferences of end-users, from field to fork. By engaging farmers directly, breeders can incorporate valuable local knowledge about environmental conditions, pest pressures, and agronomic practices, resulting in more resilient and adaptable crops. Simultaneously, involving millers, bakers, chefs, and other food industry professionals in the breeding process helps to develop varieties with desirable processing and culinary qualities. This holistic approach not only improves adoption rates of new varieties but also enhances the overall sustainability and efficiency of the food system. By aligning breeding objectives with the requirements of various stakeholders, participatory breeding fosters innovation, reduces waste, and leads to more successful and widely accepted crop varieties that benefit the entire agricultural value chain.</p>		
What is valued		
<p>Involvement^c of farmers and other actors of the value chain in cultivar development (=participatory breeding and multi-actor involvement)</p> <p>^c with involvement we intend that the people included in the breeding program at least partly are involved in the decision making for the progress of the program</p>		
How to measure		
<p style="text-align: center;">STEP 1 – breeding initiative level</p> <p style="text-align: center;">4-level scale from 1 neutral to 4 very positive</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. only breeders/scientists involved 2. low number of actor categories involvement (up to 2 categories^d beyond scientists and/or breeders) 3. medium number of actor categories involvement (3-4 actor categories) 4. High number of actor categories involvement (>= 5 actor categories) <p>^d actor categories examples: farmers, millers, food processors, citizens, policy-makers</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">STEP 2 – regional level</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>[Average number of actor categories involved in NUC breeding initiatives in the regions]</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;">Which can be compared with</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>[Average number of actor categories involved in key major crop initiatives programs in the regions]</i></p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">References</p> <p>- Colley, M.R.; Tracy, W.F.; Lammerts van Bueren, E.T.; Diffley, M.; Almekinders, C.J.M. How the Seed of Participatory Plant Breeding Found Its Way in</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Empirical data from DIVINFOOD Living Labs</p>	

<p>the World through Adaptive Management. Sustainability 2022, 14, 2132. https://doi.org/10.3390/su14042132</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Chable, V., Dawson, J., Bocci, R., Goldringer, I. (2014). Seeds for Organic Agriculture: Development of Participatory Plant Breeding and Farmers' Networks in France. In: Bellon, S., Penvern, S. (eds) Organic Farming, Prototype for Sustainable Agricultures. Springer, Dordrecht. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-7927-3_21 - Chiffolleau, Y., & Desclaux, D. (2006). Participatory plant breeding: the best way to breed for sustainable agriculture? International Journal of Agricultural Sustainability, 4(2), 119–130. https://doi.org/10.1080/14735903.2006.9684795 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Re-establishment of a value chain for the heirloom bean <i>Haricot Viande</i> in France - Participatory Breeding program on einkorn in the Living Lab Cer-Occ in France
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4.4.1 Re-establishment of a value chain for the heirloom bean *Haricot Viande* in France

The *Haricot Viande* variety was first inventoried in 1984 at Le Pinet (Puy-Saint-Pierre, 1550 masl, Hautes-Alpes). It was then inventoried again in 2015 in Saint-Aupres (Isère, 650 masl). The transcription of the ethnobotanical survey indicates that it has been cultivated for at least 60 years by the family that supplied it.

According to the inventory *Les variétés locales de plantes cultivées dans le Parc national des Ecrins*⁸ (Lagarde, M.F. & Marchenay, 1985), the name *Haricot Viande* ,i.e. 'meat bean', probably derives from its nutritional qualities and its important role after the Second World War, especially in rural areas, where it replaced meat as a source of protein. Moreover, as a dried bean, the grains were preserved for a long time in simple pots or sacks, which allowed the population to survive the winter. During the interview (of the inventory mentioned above), one of the farmers who had kept this variety for a long time (she was a woman) said "I was orphaned very early and I was always in nature reserves, and she added: "You had to survive in everything".

All these points (1) protein intake (which can replace the animal protein mostly provided by meat), (2) long conservation of dry grains, and (3) its role as food to get through the winter and finally (4) the conservation of seeds from generation to generation reported by farmers have led us to choose *Haricot Viande* to achieve the main objective of the DIVINFOOD project in Lyon Living Lab.

300g of seeds were kept in the seed bank of the CRBA, the *Centre de Ressources de Botanique Appliqués in Lyon*. They had been brought back from Chartreuse in 2017. This almost extinct variety had spent more than 60 years in mountain vegetable gardens, that of an old market gardener at an altitude of 800masl and then of a private individual who cultivated them at 450masl. The seeds were found thanks to a programme of surveying and studying the wild flora of the Chartreuse Natural Park, through the association *Semence en Montagne*.

⁸ Lagarde M.F. & Marchenay Ph., 1985. Les variétés locales de plantes cultivées dans le Parc national des Ecrins. Prospection, collecte et conservation. Paris, Gap et Dijon, CNRS, MNHN, laboratoire d'Ethnobotanique, Parc National des Ecrins, AIDEC, 236 p.

Figure 13. Plants (left) and grain (right) of *Haricot Viande* bean heirloom variety (photo: CRBA, Centre de Ressources de Botanique Appliqués in Lyon).

After evaluation in the station (at CRBA) from 2019 (before the start of the DIVINFOOD project), other good criteria have been identified (based on data collected in the field) such as (5) early maturing, (6) well adapted also to low altitude (200m), (7) fresh soft pods (like snap bean pods) and (8) very tolerant to cold, therefore less loss when pods are subjected to cold end of autumn due to late sowing or due to bad weather (resilient variety against climate change). At the same time, we proceeded screening of seeds against some bacterial diseases and in 2022, a small quantity of disease-free seeds was distributed to five farmers located at different altitudes (200 m to 800 m) and we discovered the best area for seeds with disease-free seeds in Collonges au Mont d'Or and Duerne (respectively at 200 m and 800 m altitude) in case of high incidence and/or severity of bacterial diseases.

CRBA produces basic seed each season at the station and a minimum stock (at least 5 kg) is kept in CRBA's seedbank to conserve the landrace in case of low harvest in the following season. Every year, in collaboration with mPmC s.a.s (mes Producteurs mes Cuisiniers), we identify new farmers to join the project and we follow them during the season in terms of crop and disease management, with the aim of producing beans with high quality seeds. In addition, we have carried out trials at station and farmer level: the aim is to provide answers, together with the farmers (participatory approach), to the different challenges faced by the farmers in terms of climbing bean production (activity under WP3).

In this framework, a protocol on different steps in bean seed multiplication has been elaborated by CRBA in 2023 (from site identification to harvesting). Note that up to now (2024 report) about 30% of the farmers are already producing their own seeds, whereas in the first two seasons we had to buy back (from some farmers) all the seeds they produced to have enough quantity of seeds for the next season's distribution (new and former farmers in the project).

In 2025, we are expecting to distribute seeds only to new farmers that will join the project. The LL Bean-Lyon (now extended to Région AuRA) objective (at the end of the project) is to link seed producers, grain producers (for consumption) with various other intermediaries (chefs,

restaurants) and, of course, consumers along the value chain. The story of the development of the 'Haricot Viande' variety, based on the collection and conservation of a small quantity of seeds (300 g) by the CRBA seed bank, will end with many partners who have met each other thanks to the multi-stakeholder initiative in DIVINFOOD.

In 3 years, the Région AuRA LL has put together different types of partners (including 15 farmers, 12 chefs, 12 restaurants, 2 processors).

For example, on the occasion of the Miam Festival of the Lyon Metropolis in October 2024, which was to cultivated biodiversity and organic, the starred Chef Christian Têtedoie, Meilleur Ouvrier de France and president of the association of Maîtres Cuisiniers de France, hosted a conference to present the *Haricot Viande* because of the participation to the DIVINFOOD LL. This evening event, followed by a meal, was an opportunity to review the progress of the joint work carried out over the last three years. The *Haricot Viande* were brought by the LL farmers to Chef Têtedoie to be cooked. Three courses were served at the meal, requiring 7 kg of beans for about 30 guests.

Figure 14. Chawanmushi with Haricot Viande by Chef Christian Têtedoie (photo: Laetitia Chalandon /"Mâchon pas les mots")

Thanks to the multi-actor involvement, all partners will have the opportunity to improve their interconnected activities through the network they are building together, to exchange ideas about their challenges and to find solutions together. They will undoubtedly be able to develop other projects on the theme of cultivated diversity that meet their common interests. Through the technical experience of seed and grain production, the development of new recipes for the '*Haricot Viande*' bean variety, farmers, processors, chefs and restaurants and schools will be linked. This will contribute to increasing the intake of plant proteins in the region. The DIVINFOOD multi-stakeholder project also contributes to the mobilisation of local authorities (metropolis of Lyon and other localities of the AuRA region) where activities on the cultivation and consumption of plant proteins have been and will be developed.

4.4.2 Participatory breeding program on einkorn in the Living Lab Cer-Occ in France

For two years consecutively, 102 accessions of einkorn coming from the French center of genetic resources, were sown at INRAE – Mauguio experimental station. The first year, we noted that 10% of the accessions have not germinated or present a very little vigour; and 9 accessions did not produce enough seeds because of rabbits' predation.

Twice a year, we invited farmers, technical advisers, citizens at INRAE Mauguio to assess together the phenotypic diversity of the accessions directly in the field and to identify among this diversity the varieties that could best meet their requirements. Each time, they were invited to highlight the criteria they found the most relevant for this evaluation. They focused on plant shape and discovered the high diversity: 40% of the accessions had erect tillers while 20% had tillers that covered the soil and effectively closed the inter-row. The remaining accessions displayed intermediate shapes. Further, two other parameters were highlighted: plant height and precocity. The first was measured at flowering stage and ranged between 20 and 110 cm. Precocity parameter, instead, was determined at the maturity stage, and displayed a time gap of nearly three weeks between the earliest and the latest accessions.

Alongside the French collection, 10 varieties of einkorn coming from a breeding program of European colleagues and local farmers, were also tested. These varieties were characterized by a higher height and a significant earliness when compared to the 102 accessions of the French collection. For instance, most of these varieties had already completed the flowering stage, whereas none of the accessions of the collection had reached this stage yet.

Farmers are interested in early flowering accessions, capable of covering the ground quickly to compete with weeds. They also seek for tall but lodging-resistant plants, capable of producing a substantial amount of organic matter, to increase soil fertility and to use as bedding for animals. Plant habit and height are positively correlated with the ability to compete with weeds. Einkorn is highly competitive with weeds (**Figure 15**). Indeed, more than 60% of the 112 accessions had a level higher or equal to 4, showing that this species has a good capacity to cover the soil and to close the rank, thus limiting weeds growth.

Figure 15. Percentages of the 112 accessions by score class, from 0 (not competitive), to 6 (very competitive).

Even if that was not the main concern of the farmers and citizens, they remarked that Einkorn was slightly affected by foliar diseases in comparison with modern wheat present also in the field.

It is widely recognized in the scientific literature that einkorn, along with many other ancient species/varieties, is more robust and less susceptible to pests

Farmers expressed their interest in the color of the ears, trying to maintain a diversity of red, green, and brown ears. Lastly, they were interested in the yield and the Thousand Seed Weight (TSW): indeed, due to the challenges associated with dehulling seeds and the significant role that seed weight plays in this process (larger grains are easier to extract), the TSW was considered an important criterion by farmers.

Most farmers admitted that they had not imagined such phenotypic diversity for einkorn. They had the opportunity to visit the plots, observe and compare the varieties/accessions in order to evaluate which of them could best fit the soil and climate conditions of their farm and their chain of valorization and commercialization.

As a result of this participatory evaluation, 17 accessions appeared to best match the combination of criteria that were highlighted.

Of the 17 varieties, the 8 with the highest yields were divided into 2 groups (pop1, pop2), according to their precocity.

These 17 accessions were sown on a network of agricultural plots to approach the Einkorn's capacity to adapt to a diversity of pedoclimatic environments in the Occitanie (south of France) region.

This network is made up of 8 locations: 3 are farms' sites (VT, DC, AM), 3 are located in training school (Ecole de la Raque in Castelnaudary, Lycée agricole Charlemagne in Carcassonne, Ecole de Purpan) and 2 at INRAE xperimental stations (Maug = Inrae Mauguio, AUZ = Inrae Auzeville).

Figure 16. Principal component analysis of the einkorn accessions (LL Cer-Occ)

For each criterion, interactions between accessions and locations have made it possible to identify groups of accessions. Within each group, "representative" accessions have been selected to serve as parents in the context of a selection program. Crosses are made at different farmers' sites by a farmer who has been trained in crossbreeding techniques, accompanied by researchers. This program is ongoing and each year, new crosses are realised.

4.5 Genetic material mobilisation

Indicator Card 5	Genetic material mobilisation
Background assumptions	
<p>Access to a wide spectrum of genetic resources and cultivars is essential for farmers to maintain crop diversity, adapt to changing environmental conditions and ensure food security. For NUCs often there is no available varieties in a certain region and very often it is necessary to start with commercial varieties from other regions (sometimes with very different environments) or even testing genetic resources. These steps are necessary even before considering if starting a breeding programme is useful, as in some cases adapted cultivars from regions where the crops is more used or landraces meet the need for the farmers and value chain, or are the option of choice as the breeding cost for new cultivars might be too high for the regional network.</p>	
What is valued	
Mobilisation of genetic materials (i.e. <i>in situ</i> use of genetic resources, testing and introduction of cultivars from other regions)	
How to measure	
<p style="text-align: center;">STEP 1 – breeding initiative level</p> <p style="text-align: center;">4-level scale from 1 neutral to 4 very positive</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. no genetic material mobilisation in the target region by the breeding initiative 2. low number of genetic materials provided to farmers 3. medium number of genetic materials provided to farmers 4. high number of genetic materials provided to farmers 	<p style="text-align: center;">STEP2 – regional level</p> <p><i>[Number NUC breeding initiatives providing locally tested and/or adapted genetic material in the region]</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;">Which can be compared with</p> <p><i>[Number of breeding initiatives providing locally tested and/or adapted material for the target major crop]</i></p>
References	Empirical data from DIVINFOOD Living Labs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Jérôme Enjalbert, Julie C. Dawson, Sophie Paillard, Bénédicte Rhoné, Yves Rousselle, Mathieu Thomas, Isabelle Goldringer. Dynamic management of crop diversity: From an experimental approach to on-farm conservation. <i>Comptes Rendus Biologies</i>, Volume 334, Issues 5–6, 2011, Pages 458-468, ISSN 1631-0691, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crv.2011.03.005. - Sagnard, F. et al., 2005. Ex situ and in situ genetic resource management and complementarity in participatory plant breeding, CIRAD Editions. Montpellier (France). Retrieved from https://coilink.org/20.500.12592/6ao37ml on 25 Mar 2025. COI: 20.500.12592/6ao37ml. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Expanding access to genetic resources: the case of Einkorn in south of France - Grey pea landraces in Sweden – increasing taste diversity in the plate - Faba bean – a typical feed crop that can be used for human consumption

4.5.1 Expanding access to genetic resources: the case of Einkorn in south of France

Einkorn (*Triticum monococcum* L. ssp. *monococcocum*) is considered as a NUC and listed in the INFOODS-FAO catalogue of underutilized species (<https://www.fao.org/infoods/infoods/nutrition-et-biodiversite/fr/>). However, the interest of consumers for the high nutritional quality of this cereal encourage, since few years, farmers to grow it.

A previous survey conducted in south of France showed that there is a lack of varieties suited to the different situations of production. Farmers report a very low yield and thousand grains weight, and the need to hull the grains is a real limiting factor.

Indeed, in this French area, only one variety named «*Petit Epeautre de Haute Provence*» is available and not well adapted to the diversity of farmers' environments, due to its late maturity and its low yield. Some organic farmers, millers, bakers, pasta makers, consumers, researchers, convinced by the interest of this species were involved in the CerOcc LL notably to assess a wide genetic diversity of einkorn before implementing participatory breeding programs.

The French Einkorn collection is managed by the INRAE centre of genetic resources (CRB) in Clermont Ferrand. Part of the 17,000 straw cereal accessions («varieties») are multiplied annually, so that it takes 15 years to renew the entire seed stock in the collection. For each accession, the CRB could only provide about 100 grams to each applicant.

All 102 accessions have been requested before the beginning of DIVINFOOD project. Due to the low amount of seeds only one line of sowing (5m length) for each cultivar was possible in the first year and one small plot (1.6 m x 7m), the second year. It took 3 years to get enough seeds to assess the accessions in another location and some more years to implement a field trial network. Alongside this collection, 10 varieties of einkorn coming from a breeding program of European colleagues or local farmers, were compared. One of these varieties has been identified as particularly interesting and has been the subject of a request for seeds in larger quantities. The supplier colleague informs us that «it has been registered (Plant Variety Protection) with the European Plant Variety Protection Office (CPVO) but has not yet been assigned to a seed producer». Therefore, the seeds are not available or in very small quantities, which prohibits their use by farmers.

We decided to organize a network of seed savers. Each saver multiplies 1 or more accessions the best suited to the agroenvironmental conditions. Today, 18 accessions are multiplied and are used as genitors in the participatory breeding program.

Figure 17. Each little bag corresponds to an accession given by the CRB INRAE-Clermont Ferrand (Photo: C. Debiton).

Simplified MTA to support easier genetic resources access for farmers

The objectives of the International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture were the conservation and sustainable use of plant genetic resources for food and agriculture and the fair and equitable sharing of the benefits arising from their use, in harmony with the Convention on Biological Diversity, for sustainable agriculture and food security;

Article 12.4 of the Treaty provides that facilitated access under the Multilateral System shall be in accordance with a standard Material Transfer Agreement (MTA).

The MTA ensures the traceability of the seeds and plants distributed and informs the beneficiary of his or her rights and obligations. An MTA includes various pieces of information such as the origin of the seeds, but also the rights and duties linked to their legal status, the use that will be made of them (agricultural production, experimentation - academic and small-scale - multiplication, conservation, for example), the distribution, ownership and exploitation of the results.

In the CerOcc and BeanCast LLs, the CRB managers, farmers, amateur gardeners and researchers have noted the cumbersome legal regulations concerning access to or exchange of genetic resources, which sometimes becomes an obstacle to the dissemination of diversity.

It has become essential to guarantee free access to genetic resources in order to evaluate them and possibly use them in a selection programme and, in this way, reinforce the food security of a territory. This question is all the more pressing in the context of climate change, where genetic resources can contribute to its mitigation in defined environments. The criterion of diversity then becomes essential (adaptation to drought, to disease, guarantee of ease of transformation, attractiveness to bees, mycorrhisation, etc.). The legislation governing the circulation of genetic resources must ensure the maintenance of diversity and the sustainability of agriculture, and defend the notion of the common heritage of humanity with free access to resources.

The lack of knowledge and the complexity of legal procedures sometimes demotivate those involved in the selection and conservation of genetic resources, thus generating risks of loss of diversity. The challenge was to identify the obstacles and blockages concerning the methods of transfer of genetic resources between individuals and organisations and to highlight the advantages that everyone should find in these exchanges. One of the main obstacles identified was the MTA. This contract is often very long (more than 20 pages) and can only be understood by legal specialists. We decided to rewrite a simplified MTA, based on extensive consultation with stakeholders, and to add a brochure explaining the MTA and the need to sign it.

Qu'est-ce qu'un CRB ?
C'est une infrastructure en charge de la conservation et de la gestion de collections de ressources génétiques. Les CRB se différencient selon les éléments du vivant qui y sont conservés (ressource d'origine humaine, végétale, animale, etc.) mais ils ont tous en commun l'exigence de la traçabilité du matériel conservé et distribué.

Accéder aux semences et plants conservés dans les Centres de Ressources Biologiques - CRB

Contactez-nous
CRB xxxx
XX xxxxx
xxxxxxxxxxxxx
www.xxxxx.com
Nom gestionnaire CRB
+33 x xx xx xx xx
xxxx@xxxxxx

La démarche en 6 étapes
Pensez à anticiper votre demande (étapes 2 à 5) car le processus dure au moins 3 à 4 semaines.
Mots clés pour plus d'informations sur internet : Accès semence CRB
Consulter les catalogues des différentes collections d'espèces végétales sur **FLORILÈGE**.
Pour plus de précision, contactez directement le gestionnaire du CRB concerné : indiquer l'espèce d'intérêt, les besoins agronomiques et les finalités attendues, décrire succinctement le contexte pédo-climatique.
1. J'identifie mes besoins
2. Je fais ma demande
3. Je confirme la bonne réception des semences
4. Je signe les documents et le renvoie
5. Je réponds au formulaire d'enquête et 1 an plus tard...
6. Je confirme la bonne réception des semences

Pourquoi signer un accord de transfert de matériel - MTA ?
Pour limiter les risques de biopiraterie, brevetage et appropriation, la diffusion des semences et plants est systématiquement encadrée par une réglementation visant au partage des avantages découlant de leur utilisation. Le MTA permet d'assurer la traçabilité des semences et plants distribués et d'informer le bénéficiaire de ses droits et obligations. Un MTA comporte plusieurs informations comme l'origine des semences, mais aussi des droits et des devoirs en lien avec leur statut juridique, utilisation qui en sera faite (production agricole, expérimentation - académique et paysanne- multiplication, conservation, par exemple), la distribution, la propriété et l'exploitation de résultats.
Pour en savoir plus sur les réglementations : (ajouter lien vers doc décrivant simplement les réglementations)
Le CRB a 2 semaines* pour étudier la demande et vérifier la disponibilité en stock.
• Si les semences sont disponibles, le CRB envoie par mail, un accord de transfert de matériel (ATM ou MTA) à compléter et signer.
Selon l'origine des semences, d'autres documents peuvent être nécessaires à leur diffusion. Pour plus d'informations, contacter le CRB.
Si les semences sont disponibles, le CRB envoie par mail, un accord de transfert de matériel (ATM ou MTA) à compléter et signer.
* 2 semaines* 1 mois* 1 à 2 semaines*
Afin d'enrichir les informations associées aux semences conservées et d'intégrer les données d'évaluation des demandeurs, un formulaire de retour d'expérience est à compléter et renvoyer au CRB à la suite du premier cycle de culture.

Obligations des CRB
Les CRB sont tenus de connaître l'origine des semences et plants qui composent leurs collections. Ils sont évalués sur la qualité biologique de ce qu'ils conservent mais aussi sur leur capacité à délivrer des semences et plants en assurant au bénéficiaire, leur qualité sanitaire, leur sécurité juridique et leur traçabilité.

Figure 18. Leaflet explaining what is an MTA and the need to sign it.

4.5.2 Grey pea landraces in Sweden – increasing taste diversity in the plate

Sweden has a long history of growing and eating pea – which is the most popular grain legume for human consumption that can be efficiently produced locally. Today the common type of dry pea in Sweden is round and yellow, and has an erect and semi-leafless growth habit developed for pure stand production. The semi-leafless trait was first introduced in England in 1978 and has become the predominant type of pea-type used in arable production. Before that, pea varieties

usually had a weak standing ability and benefited from a supportive crop (intercropping) for rational arable production.

Sweden has many traditional pea varieties that have been saved by farmers, seed companies, seed saver organisations, and gene banks. Many of them have a coloured seed coating and are categorised as grey peas. This type of pea has gained attention and popularity in the last decade. It is mainly produced in organic farms and is often associated with local, sustainable, culinary and cultural attributes. Some grey pea varieties were even featured in the Nobel Prize banquet dinner in 2024, which indicates their high quality / status as food ingredients. The few grey pea varieties that are available today are, however, rarely (if ever) available in super markets (except for one modern grey pea variety used in vegan meat alternatives). They are instead mostly found in restaurants, and sold to end consumers in alternative value chains – especially small organic and / or speciality shops.

Figure 19. Grey pea-based dish served at the DIVINFOOD 2024 annual meeting social dinner (photo: Dylan Wallman)

There are many more varieties of grey pea available compared to the few that are currently in active production – varieties that could contribute to future local organic production and enhance food culture. These are mainly found in gene banks and seed saver organisations (NGOs). These varieties possess a wide range of plant architectures that differ significantly from the common pea types used today, and general recommendations for pea production rarely apply to them. As mentioned, grey pea primarily refers to varieties with a coloured seed coat, and can in addition to old varieties and landraces, be found among forages peas (pea categorisation can be complicated and overlapping due to different categorisations depending on end-use). They tend to need a supportive crop for rational production on arable scale – and may be better adapted to intercropping compared to modern varieties, as modern varieties were primarily developed for pure stand production.

In LL-Leg-Nord WP4 several traditional grey pea varieties, including heritage varieties and landraces with local origin, were tested in southern Sweden. This has primarily been done in intercropping together with faba bean, which is a historical farming practise in Sweden. A subset

of varieties was also tested in pure stands to see how they perform without a supportive crop. In addition, seeds were multiplied in non-replicated larger split-plots where the same pea variety was cultivated with oat on one side and faba bean on the other, which facilitated simple comparisons between the responses of different varieties to different cropping methods. Based on the collected data, it will be easier to recommend varieties and production methods to farmers and further research. A subset of these varieties were selected for on-farm trials in WP3 and will continue for culinary testing in WP2.

The wide range of plant architectures within this category of pea has shown to be a potential asset in designing and exploring different types of intercropping. The different varieties have different maturity times making them compatible for intercropping with different species (e.g. oat matures earlier and faba bean later). They have also indicated different tendencies to withstand drought scenarios during the years of evaluation in WP4 (2023 had a very dry early summer in Sweden). Most of the tested varieties has potential to be produced on arable scale, however, great care should be taken when designing the system, with primary criteria being choice of companion species and variety, seeding ratio, maturity time, and seed size. The diversity between the different grey pea varieties may increase chances of finding growth habits that have a higher degree of complementarity to the companion crop in intercropping systems, compared to only using a modern standard type of pea.

4.5.3 Faba bean – a typical feed crop that can be used for human consumption

Faba bean (*Vicia faba*) is another grain legume (alongside pea) with a long history of cultivation and use in Sweden. It has been produced both as a garden crop and on arable scale, and has been used for both food and feed. In modern times, the arable production has primarily been focused on small seeded varieties for animal feed. It has, however, been acknowledged that this type of faba bean could be an excellent alternative as a locally produced plant-based protein alternative used directly for human consumption. In fact, it is already a common food ingredient in Middle East and North Africa, and re-introducing faba bean in the Nordic cuisine is a logical step in transitioning to more sustainable food production and consumption.

In LL-Faba-Nord WP4 we tested three different types of faba bean in both pure stand and in intercropping with pea. These experiments were conducted in southern Sweden. They included varieties differing in agronomical features such as plant length, maturity time, flowering time, and seed size. 'Birgit' is a typical variety used contemporarily in local organic farming; 'Kontu' is an early maturing variety from Finland with a small plant size; and 'Solberga' is a Swedish landrace that was traditionally intercropped with pea and has a history of human consumption. The latter is a rare landrace and there was barely enough seed for it to be used at the start of this project – we therefore multiply seed in order to use it for an on-farm trial in WP3, and culinary testing in WP2.

Figure 20. The three faba bean varieties tested in Sweden for WP4 (LL-Faba-Nord) (photo: Dylan Wallman)

4.6 Small and medium scale entrepreneurship in the breeding and seed sector and in rural areas

Indicator Card 6	Small and medium scale entrepreneurship in the breeding and seed sector and in rural areas
Background assumptions	
<p>NUCs breeding is the opportunity for small and medium scale companies (SMEs) and non-profit organisations to develop in the breeding and seed sector, as NUCs are of limited or no interest for large breeding firms. NUCs breeding thus contributes to rebalance powers in the breeding sectors. Moreover, seed production and breeding can be a significant opportunity for SMEs entrepreneurship in rural areas, especially for minor crops. Small seed companies can respond to specific local needs, particularly for minor crops that are often overlooked by larger commercial seed companies. This fills an important gap in the seed market, giving farmers access to locally adapted and preferred varieties. Farmers, cooperatives and SMEs can generate significant income by producing and selling seed in local markets. This can lead to the establishment of small and medium scale initiatives that serve local markets and enter into seed production contracts with various stakeholders. This entrepreneurial activity with decentralised breeding and seed production initiatives can significantly improve rural livelihoods.</p> <p>Small seed companies have a marketing advantage because they operate in viable market catchment areas, enabling them to meet the seed needs of rural farmers more effectively. They often offer a more diverse range of varieties than larger seed companies.</p> <p>Seed production initiatives can be integrated into broader rural development programmes, often supported by NGOs and grassroots initiatives.</p>	
What is valued	
<p>Counter-balancing the very strong market concentration of the breeding and seed sector. Small and medium scale entrepreneurship in rural areas based on breeding and seed production</p>	
How to measure	
<p>STEP 1 – breeding initiative level</p> <p>4-options (2-3-4 equally positive)</p>	<p>STEP 2 – regional level</p>

<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. global company 2. public research/breeding organisation 3. non-profit initiative 4. SME (small-medium enterprise) 	<p style="text-align: center;"><i>[Number of SMEs, research and non-profit organisations breeding NUCs or producing NUC seeds in the region]</i></p> <hr style="width: 20%; margin: auto;"/> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>[Total number of NUCs breeding and seed initiatives in the region]</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;">Which can be compared with</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>[Number of SMEs, research and non-profit organisation breeding or producing seeds of the target major crop in the region]</i></p> <hr style="width: 20%; margin: auto;"/> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>[Total number of breeding and seed initiatives of the target major crop in the region]</i></p>
References	Empirical data from DIVINFOOD Living Labs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In the map of organic breeders in Europe by biobreeding.org one can find several cases of small seed initiatives in rural areas https://www.biobreeding.org/breeding.html 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Biosaat, an example of seed enterprises for organically bred varieties - An example in the south of France: “Les Maîtres de mon Moulin”

4.6.1 Biosaat, an example of seed enterprise for organically bred varieties

Biosaat GmbH ([biosaat.eu](https://www.biosaat.eu)) distributes organically bred varieties from breeders gzpk in Switzerland and Dottenfelderhof and Cultivari in Germany. Their core business is the supply of basic and pre-basic seed. They also organise, coordinate and support the propagation process. This enables their partners in the different regions to supply farmers with high quality seed in the best possible way - in Germany and Europe. Although Biosaat is not directly part of DIVINFOOD LL, FiBL's white lupin breeding programme is run in collaboration with the non-profit, independent breeding organisation gzpk, which is Biosaat's partner. Together, gzpk and Biosaat are demonstrating the potential for rural entrepreneurship in the area of variety development and seed sales in the organic sector, with a particular focus on NUCs.

4.6.2 An example in the south of France: “Les Maîtres de mon Moulin”

At the beginning it was a small company that restored an old windmill and decided to ground organic cereal grains on this stone mill. Very quickly, they only ground grains of "ancient" varieties of soft wheat and durum wheat then diversified towards NUCs such as einkorn, rivet wheat, etc, and became bakers and pasta makers. Today, faced with the increase in demand for their product, they have brought together a network of farmers around the mill and have become multipliers of ancient varieties to supply their network with clean, sorted, fair and healthy seeds.

<https://www.agriterra-group.com/fr/tous-nos-projets/les-maitres-de-mon-moulin-semences-anciennes>

Figure 21. Farmers and researchers from France and Algeria jointly evaluate different varieties of einkorn located on the “Les maîtres de mon Moulin” seed platform. The windmill is visible at the top of the hill (Photo: D. Desclaux).

4.7 Farmer capacity building in breeding

Indicator Card 7	Farmer capacity building in breeding
Background assumptions	
<p>Working with farmers on variety selection and seeds through participatory approaches can serve as a transformative entry point for rethinking the entire agro-food system. By involving farmers directly in decision-making processes, such as participatory breeding and community seed banks, we empower them to take ownership of their agricultural practices, fostering resilience and sustainability. Seeds, as the foundation of agriculture, are not only a critical resource but also a vehicle for capacity building within farming communities, enabling knowledge exchange and innovation. Importantly, this approach highlights the potential where skills such as seed-saving practices, crossings, selection steps directly by farmers can inform and inspire more sustainable cultivar development.</p>	
What is valued	
<p>Developing opportunities of growth and further development of sustainable agriculture approaches based on the co-creation activities in the topic of seeds and breeding</p>	
How to measure	
<p style="text-align: center;">STEP 1 - breeding initiative level</p> <p style="text-align: center;">4-level scale from 1 neutral to 4 very positive</p> <p>1. no capacity building (in breeding and seed production) for farmers organised by the breeding initiative</p> <p>2. low level of capacity building (in breeding and seed production) for farmers organised by the breeding initiative</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">STEP2 - regional level</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>[Number of NUC breeding initiatives doing farmer medium-high capacity building in the region]</i></p> <hr style="width: 20%; margin: auto;"/> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>[Total number of NUC breeding initiatives in the region]</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;">Which can be compared with</p>

<p>3. medium level of capacity building (in breeding and seed production) for farmers organised by the breeding initiative</p> <p>4. high level of capacity building (in breeding and seed production) for farmers organised by the breeding initiative</p>	<p><i>[Number of major crop breeding initiatives doing farmer medium-high capacity building]</i></p> <hr/> <p><i>[Total number of breeding initiatives of the target major crop in the region]</i></p>
<p>References</p>	<p>Empirical data from DIVINFOOD Living Labs</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Colley et al (2021). Exploring the emergence of participatory plant breeding in countries of the Global North – a review. <i>The Journal of Agricultural Science</i>. 159(5-6):320-338. doi:10.1017/S0021859621000782 - Colley et al. (2022). How the Seed of Participatory Plant Breeding Found Its Way in the World through Adaptive Management. <i>Sustainability</i>, 14(4), 2132. https://doi.org/10.3390/su14042132 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Capacity building by in organic cereal production in France

4.7.1 Capacity building in organic cereal production in France

The participatory breeding dynamic developed within the LLs CerOcc and BeanCast contributes greatly to strengthening the autonomy of farmers, and their independence from the dominant system (big cooperatives and traders, seed and agrochemical companies, agricultural equipment manufacturers, etc.). Farmers are supported by INRAE researchers and by Biocivam11, an association supporting agroecological agriculture. This breeding activity is part of a broader dynamic that includes issues surrounding the sorting, storage, processing, cooking and sale of cereals in short chains. All these "environments", very different from those usually encountered by "conventional" farmers, generate new questions about the most relevant criteria and methods for improving plants. Farmers therefore wanted to select and evaluate their varieties not only on criteria easily observable with the naked eye (height of the straw, weight of a grain, colour of the ear, shape of the plant, ease of hulling, etc.) but also on root criteria (number of mychoryzae present on the roots). Training courses are regularly offered in classrooms, in the farm fields, or in bakeries and are an opportunity for real exchanges between practitioners. Farmers are regularly invited to the research institute laboratories for example to observe the mycorrhizal capacity of their cereals under the microscope.

Figure 22. Observation of einkorn roots (left, Photo : C. Shigo) and *photo of einkorn arbusculae* (right, Photo: D. Desclaux)

4.8 Citizen awareness raising on agrobiodiversity benefits

Indicator Card 8	Citizen awareness raising on agrobiodiversity benefits
Background assumptions	
<p>According to the results of DIVINFOOD WP1 on consumers attitude, the link between (agro)biodiversity and food choice is a complex issue that is often difficult for consumers to grasp. Consumers typically do not make a direct link between the conservation and management of agrobiodiversity and their food choices. Many are unaware of the distinction between species diversity and variety diversity, making communication about crop diversification in general and genetic diversity in particular difficult. In addition, it is difficult to explain the need for and benefits of novel adapted materials such as Organic Heterogeneous Material (OHM) or Organic Varieties (OV) as not conflicting with the conservation of genetic resources. When buying fresh produce, and even more so for processed foods, variety selection is rarely a decisive factor for consumers. Attempts to highlight plant species names (such as underutilised and neglected crops) or varieties (such as landraces or organic varieties) on food packaging often prove ineffective. Furthermore, while promoting variety names through targeted campaigns may seem beneficial, it may be counterproductive in the long run, as breeding is an ongoing process aimed at continuously developing new and adapted varieties to meet evolving needs.</p> <p>To effectively communicate the link between (agro)biodiversity and food choice, it's important to focus on aspects that resonate with consumers.</p> <p>Awareness raising should highlight the sensory attributes of different varieties, such as taste, appearance and texture, to make diversity more tangible and appealing to consumers. It's also important to recognise that consumers are most likely to encounter new species or varieties at farmers' markets, in restaurants or through produce box schemes. These are prime opportunities for raising awareness. For products sold through shops, consumer groups or online platforms, the development of clear and easy-to-understand messages on labels is crucial.</p> <p>By focusing on networking with stakeholders across the value chain and focusing on crops with high conservation value, NUC breeding can effectively communicate the importance of (agro)biodiversity while appealing to consumers' interests in taste, nutrition and sustainability, thereby encouraging more diverse food choices.</p>	
What is valued	
Effort to increase citizen awareness of agrobiodiversity benefits	
How to measure	
<p>STEP 1- breeding initiative level</p> <p style="text-align: center;">level scale from 1 neutral to 4 very positive</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. no citizen awareness raising effort by the breeding initiative 2. low level of citizen awareness raising effort by the breeding initiative 3. medium level of citizen awareness raising effort by the breeding initiative 4. high level of citizen awareness raising effort by the breeding initiative 	<p style="text-align: center;">STEP 2 – regional level</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>[Number of NUC breeding initiatives in the region doing medium-high effort to increase citizens awareness]</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;">Which can be compared with</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>[Number of target major crop breeding initiatives doing medium-high effort to increase citizens awareness]</i></p>
References	Empirical data from DIVINFOOD Living Labs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Chiffolleau, Y., Dourian, T., Enderli, G., Mattioni, D., Akermann, G., Loconto, A., Galli, F., Emese, G., Perényi, Z., Colombo, L., Massari, S., & Desclaux, D. (2024). Reversing the trend of agrobiodiversity decline by co-developing food chains with consumers: A European survey for 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Raise consumer awareness of lupin and neglected grain legumes in general in Switzerland - Raise consumer awareness of neglected crops breeding in south of France

<p>change. Sustainable Production and Consumption, 46(February), 343–354. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2024.02.032</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - RightSeeds - https://uol.de/en/wire/economy-of-the-commons/junior-research-group-rightseeds ; - LIVESEED - www.liveseed.eu and Engagement.Biobreeding - www.biobreeding.org ; - DIVERSIFOOD - diversifood.eu. - DYNAVERSITY - dynaversity.eu - Enagement & Benefits biobreeding – biobreeding.org 	
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4.8.1 Raise consumer awareness of lupin and neglected grain legumes in general in Switzerland

It is very important to work on the value chain when developing new varieties of underutilised crops. FiBL contributes to the establishment of a network for domestic grain legumes cultivation by bringing together relevant value-chain stakeholders to build a market for the re-introduction of lupin in Switzerland.

The awareness raising activities include the active participation to the Swiss *Netzwerk Protein Power*, i.e. Protein Power Network.

The Protein Power Network is a platform for people from the entire value chain in Switzerland who focus on the production and processing of plant-based proteins for human nutrition. One of its aims is to enable Swiss agriculture to benefit from the increased demand for plant-based proteins. The network is open to anyone who works in the production and marketing of plant-based proteins, has an advisory role or is personally interested.

The Protein Power network places a particular focus on collaborative learning through cooperation and the exchange of experiences. Participants can deepen and broaden their knowledge and consolidate fundamentals by exchanging experiences and best practices. Participants work together to develop solutions for common problems and goals, drawing on the expertise of the participants.

The Protein Power Network provides a platform for innovation, knowledge sharing and collaboration to improve and expand the production and processing of plant-based proteins in Switzerland.

FiBL maintains the platform Legume Hub SWISS <https://swiss.legumehub.eu/>. The platform on the site helps to successfully grow, process and market legumes. Disease-resistant varieties and knowledge of how to grow them in a location-appropriate manner are needed; the harvested crop must meet the quality requirements for processing and fit the needs of the market. All of this requires not only knowledge transfer but also experience, research and political action.

As well, work directly with consumers is fundamental. The biobreeding initiative by FiBL has the objective to increase awareness about cultivated diversity along the value chain with communications products such as a video about organic breeding <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=o31AZM-mes> and a flyer to explain the connection between seed diversity and food diversity <https://zenodo.org/records/13629461>.

Activities tailored to DIVINFOOD included participation in events presenting the benefits of grain legumes and food tastings to raise awareness through tasting the culinary products, such as at the Organic Legumes Day in 2024 (**Figure 23**) and the Biodiversity market 1001 vegetables 2024 (Vielfaltsmarkt 1001 Gemüse 2024 <https://1001gemuese.ch/>). In these events the tasting activities are used to engage citizens into a conversation about lupins and grain legumes in general.

Figure 23. “Farinata” degustation during the BioLeguminosenTag 2025 (Day of Organic Legumes 2025, Photo: Mariateresa Lazzaro, FiBL).

For example, at the Day of Organic Legumes 2025, the culinary highlight of the day was a tasting of Italian “farinata”, a flatbread traditionally made from chickpeas in three varieties: chickpeas, peas and grass pea. White lupines were available as a snack in the form of beans, as crackers and as a spread. Participants could taste the three types and vote for the most liked one.

4.8.2 Raise consumer awareness of neglected crops breeding in South of France

Several Science and Society events have been held to increase exchanges between researchers and civil society on topics related to plant breeding.

Among them, we can notably mention:

- **The Kfé workshops**

INRAE organized monthly workshops (“kfé”, for *coffee break*) by videoconference lasting 1h30, on a theme concerning plant or animal breeding (one of the objectives was also to make a link between the animal “world” and the plant “world” regarding breeding). For each “kfé”, one or two speakers were invited to present the subject for 10 to 15 minutes and then a discussion was organised in the plenary room or by group.

Fifteen video cafés were held between January 2023 and July 2024 (All the replays are available on the site <https://metabio.hub.inrae.fr/thematiques/gestion-des-ressources/incubiobreeding-consortium-2023-2024>)

Figure 24. Flyer announcing the Kfé on NGT (new genomic techniques)

The 15 kfés brought together a total of 331 people, 56% of whom came from the world of research and education and 44% from farmers and citizens. In addition, partnerships with technical agricultural education were established, thus promoting connections with Research.

47% of people connected at least twice. The average participation was between 30 and 50 with the maximum of 150 people for the theme of NGT (new genomic techniques) topic, in relation with the DIVINFOOD project.

- **Street interviews contributed to the inclusion of citizens in the project**

The aim was to give citizens a voice on the subject of food and to raise their awareness of livestock farming. To do this, the following two questions were asked: *‘If organic farming becomes the majority in the future, what obstacles and incentives do you foresee?’* and *“Do you think we have the varieties and seeds necessary for this?”* were asked to people leaving a specialised organic shop (in Montpellier, located in the LL CerOcc region) on Friday 5 May 2023 from 4.30 pm onwards. The time was chosen to benefit from a diversity of profiles (students, parents, the elderly, etc.) and to have time for discussion. The responses were recorded with the consent of the respondents. This recording was first transcribed in full, then reworked into a soundtrack. It has been posted online.

- **Interviews during field days**

Three themed days: the ‘Faites des haricots’ (‘Make Beans’) day organised on Saturday 22 April 2023 (in Castelnaudary) and the Forgotten Cereals Days (organised on Thursday 8 June 2023 and 10 June 2024 at the Lamothe experimental farm of the Purpan-Toulouse School of Engineering) have provided an opportunity to meet various stakeholders (farmers, teachers, researchers, advisers, citizens, etc.) and to discuss breeding and organic farming with them, followed by workshops on these topics.

Figure 25. Example of interviews during field days in South France.

- **Awareness-raising workshops on the issues surrounding seeds and varieties with residents of priority districts**

Events were organized in conjunction with a variety of associations to raise awareness among the general public about the challenges of seeds and varieties and the link between food and seeds.

Figure 26. Discussion on plant breeding during the cooking workshop with “Cuisine d’ailleurs” (Photo: D.Desclaux (left), MF Samson (right)).

A first meeting took place at the Asylum Seekers Reception Center (CADA) in Béziers (<https://www.lacimade.org/nos-actions/hebergement-langue-francaise/le-centre-dhebergement-de-beziers/>) with the association "Cuisine d'ailleurs" which organises cooking

workshops to create links between people accommodated at the CADA and people in the neighborhood. We organized 2 workshops, on March 26 and July 2, 2024, which allowed during the preparation of the meal and during the meal, to discuss the foods present on the plate, their origin, the way of producing them, up to the types of varieties, and seeds used. Organic market gardeners had been invited so that together we could think about access for people in food insecurity to organic and healthy products.

Three events were organized with the Jasmin d'Orient association (<https://www.jasmindorient.fr/>), an association from a priority district of Montpellier, which aims to be a bridge between the East and the West and which seeks to promote the integration of women from Maghreb countries.

Figure 27. Presentation of seeds during the “Eat Well, Live Well” festival- Montpellier-France (left) and during the during the "Sport and Well-being" day (Photo: D.Desclaux).

A first animation took place on Friday, April 26, 2024 as part of the “Eat Well, Live Well” festival organized by this Jasmin d'Orient association for the children of the Diderot elementary school in Montpellier. The objective of the animation was to recreate the links between the field and the plate. To do this, the children had to identify the ingredients present in a couscous dish and then find the photos of the corresponding plants and seeds. We also provided the children with small pots, soil and seeds, explaining to them where the seeds came from.

The second event took place on Wednesday, May 22, 2024 in the St Martin district of Montpellier during the "Sport and Well-being" day organized by Sport Hérault and the Jasmin d'Orient association. The activity offered a question-and-answer game. A carpet dotted with colored circles was placed on the ground. When the child had to balance his hand or foot on a color, a question on a theme around food and seeds was asked. Another activity took place on Friday, July 5, 2024 in a public garden in Montpellier as part of the "Au rythme de la ville" festival. The objective was to discuss with the general public about new genomic techniques and their compatibility with organic farming.

Figure 28. Discussion with families on NGT (July 5, 2024, Photo: D. Desclaux (left), C.Shigo (right))

- **Meeting with high school students**

In collaboration with high school biology teachers, we gave a presentation in a final year class specializing in life and earth sciences to present plant improvement from the domestication of plants to modern agriculture. This intervention was prepared with scientific mediators who had created an activity on the domestication of plants from the Neolithic period to the present day.

Figure 29. Meeting with high school students on plant breeding (Photo: T.Dainat)

4.9 Values of the SMART indicators for the DIVINFOOD Living Labs

The DIVINFOOD LL coordinators, in collaboration with the partners involved in the selection and breeding activities of the project (WP4) when applicable, have self-evaluated their networks based on the STEP 1 (breeding initiative level) measurement scale for each indicator. From **Table 2** it is possible to highlight key strengths of each LL.

Table 2 List of proposed Self-evaluation for the STEP 1 or each indicator by each LL in DIVINFOOD.

	Indicators	1. Bean-Lyon	2. Bean-Cast	3. Cer-Occ (Poulard wheat)	3. Cer-Occ (Einkorn)	4- Leg-ItSwitz (Italy)	4- Leg-ItSwitz (Switzerland)	5. GPea-Port	6. FabaNord	7. Leg-Nord (Denmark)	7. Leg-Nord (Sweden)	8. Leg-Hung	9. Cer-Hung
1	Agroecological breeding environments	2	3	2	4	3	4	3	2	3	2	1	4
2	Genetic diversity within cultivars	1	3	2	3	2	4	3	2	3	3	2	4
3	Added-value target traits	3	1	3	4	2	2	3	2	3	2	2	3
4	Multi-Actor involvement	3	3	2	4	3	1	2	1	2	2	3	3
5	Genetic material mobilisation	2	4	2	4	2	2	2	3	3	3	3	2
6	SMEs in the breeding and seed sector	na	2	4	2	2	3	2	1	na	2	4	2
7	Farmer capacity building in breeding	1	3	2	3	2	1	3	1	3	2	3	3
8	Citizen awareness on agrobiodiversity	4	2	3	4	2	3	3	1	2	3	4	4

5. Conclusion

Investing in (i) genetic resources characterisation, maintenance and cultivation, (2) selections from available materials and (3) breeding programmes to develop new varieties for NUCs can yield significant economic, environmental, and societal benefits. The eight indicators described in this report help to promote such benefits among farmers, breeders, seed producers, food processors, citizens (STEP 1 measurement) and policy makers (STEP 2 measurement).

In terms of **Economic Benefits**, access to improved NUC seeds offer farmers the potential for additional income streams, reducing their reliance on a limited number of major crops. The development of high-quality NUC varieties can lead to the creation of new market niches as well as new seed producing opportunities (**SMART indexes 4-Multi-actor involvement, 6- Small and medium scale entrepreneurship in the breeding and seed sector and in rural areas, 7- Farmer capacity building in breeding**). Many NUCs require fewer inputs compared to major crops, which can potentially lower production costs for farmers (**SMART index 1- Agroecological breeding environments**). Furthermore, improved NUCs can serve as raw materials for value-added products, creating economic opportunities along the entire value chain (**SMART index 3- Added-value target traits**). This diversification and value addition can contribute to more resilient and profitable agricultural systems.

Regarding **Environmental Benefits** promoting NUCs enhances overall agricultural biodiversity, contributing to more resilient ecosystems (**SMART indexes 1- Agroecological breeding environments, 2- Genetic diversity within cultivars, 3- Added-value target traits, 5-Genetic resources mobilisation**). Many NUCs are naturally adapted to marginal and difficult environments, making them valuable resources for climate change adaptation. NUCs often require fewer agrochemicals and are suited to low-input agriculture, reducing the environmental footprint of farming. Diverse cropping systems that include NUCs can provide enhanced ecosystem services.

The **Social Benefits** of delivering adapted NUC varieties include contributing to both better dietary value and diversity (**SMART index 4-Multi-actor involvement**). Promoting NUCs helps preserve traditional knowledge and cultural practices associated with these crops, as well as an occasion for cultural exchange between traditional and new cultivation areas (**SMART indexes 8-Citizen awareness on agrobiodiversity benefits**). Focusing on NUCs can create new opportunities for rural communities, supporting livelihoods and reducing rural abandonment (**SMART indexes 6- Small and medium scale entrepreneurship in the breeding and seed sector and in rural areas, 7- Farmer capacity building in breeding**).

6. Appendixes

Appendix 1. Description of DIVINFOOD Living Labs.....	54
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Appendix 1 Description of DIVINFOOD Living Labs

Name of the LL (GxE)	NUCs considered (G)	Specific challenges	Size and location of the LL (E)	Climatic zone(E)
Bean-Lyon	'Meat bean', (<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i>)	Rehabilitation of local and traditional, yet forgotten, bean cultivars	69.700 km ² Lyon and its nearby departments including Ain, Rhone and Isère	Continental
Bean-Cast	Lingot bean (<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i>)	Cultivars adapted to organic conditions	2.400 km ² Lauragais- Castelnaudary in region Occitanie, Southern France	Mediterranean
Cer-Occ	Einkorn (<i>Triticum monococcum</i>) Rivet wheat (<i>Triticum turgidum</i>)	Cultivars better adapted to drought	72.700 km ² Region Occitanie , Southern France	Mediterranean
Leg-ItSwitz	White lupin (<i>Lupinus albus</i>)	Development of new varieties with increased stress and disease tolerance and low alkaloid content. Conservation of landraces. Optimisation of cultivation.	191.300 km ² Central and Northern Italy and Switzerland	Humid Continental - Mediterranean
GPea-Port	Grass pea (<i>Lathyrus sativus</i>)	New varieties and intercropping	160 km ² Region Alvaiazere , Central-Northern Portugal	Mediterranean
Faba-Nord	Faba bean (<i>Vicia faba</i>)	Adapted varieties	292.900 km ² Denmark, Sweden	Oceanic, humid continental

Leg-Nord	Narrowleaved Lupin (<i>Lupinus angustifolius</i>), Grey pea (<i>Pisum Sativum subsp. Arvense</i>), Lentils (<i>Lens culinaris</i>)	Adapted varieties	292.900 km ² Denmark, Sweden	Oceanic, Humid continental
Leg-Hung	Lentil (<i>Lens culinaris</i>) Dry pea or yellow pea (<i>Pisum sativum ssp. sativum convar. sativum</i>) Cowpea (<i>Vigna unguiculata</i>) Chickpea (<i>Cicer arietinum</i>)	Adapted and drought tolerant cultivars	93.000 km ² Hungary	Dry Continental-Mediterranean
Cer-Hung	Emmer (<i>Triticum dicoccum</i>) Einkorn (<i>Triticum monococcum</i>)	Adapted cultivars selected from landraces	93.000 km ² Hungary	Dry Continental-Mediterranean

